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***Preparation, in-vitro evaluation and pharmaco-
dynamic study of minoxidil topical nanoemulsion-
based gel***

A thesis

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Dedication.....

To...

The spirit of my father ...

My beloved mother, sister, brothers ...

My dear wife, Sada

***To the hope of my life, my beloved daughters, Rama
and Leen...***

I dedicate this work with my love.

Alaa Rakan Altaie

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Abstract

Androgenetic alopecia is a common type of hair loss and a very common dermatological disorder. Minoxidil is a potent vasodilator that has been approved by the FDA as a topical solution or foam for the treatment of androgenetic alopecia. However, the delivery of minoxidil from conventional topical solutions suffered from short contact time with the scalp, poor drug penetration, and high dose requirements

This work aims to prepare an o/w nanoemulsion-based gel of minoxidil to prolong contact time with the scalp and possible enhanced pharmaco-dynamic effects.

Preliminary studies were conducted to make a suitable selection of oil phase, surfactant and surfactant/co-surfactant ratios. Eight formulae of minoxidil loaded nanoemulsion were prepared and subjected to different investigational studies such as measurement of pH, electrical conductivity, percent of light transmittance, drug content and entrapment efficiency, droplet size, polydispersity, zeta potential, and thermodynamic stability studies to determine the optimum formula. Then, the selected formula is subjected to further studies such as in-vitro drug release, transmission electron microscopy and pharmaco-dynamics studies.

Moreover, in the second part of the study, three different minoxidil-loaded nanoemulgel formulae were prepared by using the selected formula of nanoemulsion with three different concentrations of carbopol 934. The prepared nanoemulgel formulae were further subjected to characterization studies such as drug-excipient compatibility study by Fourier Transform Infrared Spectroscopy (FTIR), measurement of pH, spreadability, viscosity, in-vitro drug release, permeation studies and stability study under different storage conditions to determine the best minoxidil-loaded nanoemulgel formula.

The results of characterization showed that the minoxidil loaded nanoemulsion NE-A2 formula with Smix ratio (2:1), 5% oil concentration, and 40% Smix concentration was the optimized formula (hydrodynamic diameter of 14.62 ± 1.36 nm, PDI of 0.22 ± 0.021 , Zeta potential of -4.7 ± 0.6 mV and entrapment efficiency of $91.2 \pm 0.31\%$). The results of The EM of the selected formula showed spherical droplets that appeared to be less than 100 nm. The pharmaco-dynamic study showed that the average relaxation percentage for optimized nanoemulsion formula NE-A2 was equal to $76.73 \pm 7.490\%$ while that for the marketed solution was $14.59 \pm 1.233\%$.

The characterization results of the optimized minoxidil-loaded nanoemulgel formula NEG-A2y demonstrated that the formula has an acceptable pH value with optimum spreadability (21.6 ± 0.70 g.cm/s), and optimum viscosity (492 ± 87.81 cp) for nanoemulgel to be applied topically. The in-vitro release profile of the optimized minoxidil-loaded nanoemulsion formula NE-A2 has a higher release than that of standard solution and marketed solution at 420 minutes, and it was noticed that the cumulative release profile of optimized minoxidil-loaded nanoemulgel formula NEG-A2y is slower than that of alcoholic standard solution and marketed solution. Based on the permeation study results, the optimized nanoemulgel formula NEG-A2y exhibited a better permeation profile than the marketed solution and the cumulative amount of MXD that permeated through the skin over 24 hours from the NEG-A2y formula was 961.97 ± 4.77 $\mu\text{g}/\text{cm}^2$, which is significantly ($P \leq 0.05$) higher than that from the marketed solution, 398.24 ± 10.03 $\mu\text{g}/\text{cm}^2$. The nanoemulgel formula NEG-A2y was checked for stability, and it was shown that the formula is stable at different temperatures.

The current study concludes that nanoemulgel is considered an advanced technique for enhancing delivery with the prolonged contact time, enhanced permeation, and consequent enhanced pharmaco-dynamic effect of minoxidil.

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LIST OF ABBREVIATIONS

Abbreviation	Meaning
ANOVA	Analysis of variance
API(s)	Active Pharmaceutical Ingredient(s)
Conc.	Concentration
cp	Centipoise
DDS	Drug delivery system
DLS	Dynamic light scattering
DW	Distilled water
EE	Entrapment efficiency
FDA	Food and Drug Administration
FTIR	Fourier Transform Infrared Spectroscopy
HDD	Hydrodynamic diameter
HLB	Hydrophilic – lipophilic Balance
IR	Infrared
Kp	Permeability coefficient
kV	KiloVolte
Log p	The logarithm of partition coefficient
M.wt	Molecular weight
mV	Millivolt
MXD	Minoxidil
NE(s)	Nanoemulsion (s)
NEG	Nanoemulgel
nm	Nanometer
PDI	Polydispersity Index

PG	Propylene glycol
pH	Measurement of acidity or basicity of liquids
PIC	Phase inversion composition
PIT	Phase inversion temperature technique
Psi	Pound per square inch
P-value	Probability value
r^2	The correlation coefficient
rpm	Round per minute
Smix	A mixture of surfactant and co-surfactant
SC	Stratum corneum
SCTs	Short-chain triglycerides
SD	Standard Deviation
SSTF	Steady-state transdermal flux
TEM	Transmission electron microscopy
Tween 20 [®]	Polyoxyethylene sorbitan mono-laurate
Tween 80 [®]	Polyoxyethylene sorbitan mono-oleate
U.S.P	United States Pharmacopeia
UV	Ultraviolet
v/v	Volume /volume
w/o	Water in oil
w/v	Weight/volume
w/w	Weight/weight
ZP	Zeta potential
λ_{max}	Maximum wavelength absorbance
$\mu\text{S/cm}$	Micro Siemens per centimeter
T%	Percent of Light Transmittance

(Chapter One)

Introduction

1 Introduction

Hair is an essential part of the human body that brings self-esteem and confidence to both genders. People wish to have elegant, healthy, and thick head hair because hair has a great impact on the beauty and social life (1). Hair is considered as protective appendages along with sweat glands, sebaceous glands and nails known as epidermal derivatives (2).

1.1 Hair structure

Hair is composed of proteins, keratin, lipids, water, pigments, and other trace elements. Structurally, hair is divided into the bulb, the root and the stem, which is embedded in the dermis. The bulb is the deepest region, which is responsible for hair growth. It is linked to dermal papillae, a highly vascularized area, which permits transportation of nutrients to the hair. The root is firmly attached to the hair follicle (3). Both the root and the stem are known as hair shafts and they are formed by 3 concentric layers: the medulla, cortex and cuticle. The cortex is the thickest part of hair fiber and is responsible for the mechanical properties while the cuticle acts as a barrier that protects the hair fiber from the external environment (4). The structure of hair is shown in **Figure (1.1)** (4).

Figure (1.1) The structure of hair (4).

1.2 Hair follicle cycle

Hair follicles, which are distributed throughout the body surface and the continuous cycle of hair follicles, include 3 phases of growth (anagen), involution (catagen) and rest (telogen). The first phase is the productive stage, usually, this phase lasts about 2-3 years. In the second phase, the hair follicle involutes and, normally, this phase lasts 2-3 weeks. The last phase is telogen and is known as the resting stage. It lasts 2-3 months. In the normal hair cycle, the anagen to telogen ratio is 12:1. Therefore, the duration of the anagen phase is the major determinant of hair length (5).

1.3 Hair loss or alopecia

Alopecia is one of the most common dermatological disorders of many communities. It causes many economical and psychological problems. There are many types of alopecia, the most common type is known as androgenetic alopecia (AGA) or Male pattern hair loss (MPHL) (6). AGA is a progressive and patterned hair loss from the scalp, that takes place in genetically susceptible individuals. AGA is widespread and its incidence rises with age, affecting 58% of males over 50 years and 57% of women over 80 years old (7).

AGA is an androgen-dependent condition, and it starts soon after puberty. Many studies suggested that baldness occurs because of increased concentration of dihydrotestosterone (DHT) and androgenic receptors. Although the pathogenic mechanism of AGA is not fully discovered, there are several studies showed that AGA promotes hair follicle shrinkage, reduces hair density, and increases the appearance of weak vellus hair. The shortening of the anagen phase leads to a drop in the hair density and a decrease in the diameter of the hair follicle (reduced thickness) (8).

1.4 Pharmacological therapy

Patients with hair loss have a variable response to the medical treatments, which include oral, topical Minoxidil (MXD), oral 5 alpha-reductase inhibitors (finasteride), growth factors and oral and topical prostaglandins (latanoprost). However, the only FDA approved drugs for the treatment of AGA are oral finasteride and topical MXD (9).

1.5 Minoxidil (MXD) properties

MXD is a piperidino-pyrimidine derivative (2,4-diamino-6 piperidino-pyrimidine-3-oxide) with a chemical formula $C_9H_{15}N_5O$, M.wt. equal to 209.25 gm/mole and the chemical structure is shown in **Figure (1.2)**. MXD has a log p equal to 1.24, MXD is slightly soluble in water (water solubility equal to 2.2 mg/ml) and belongs to BCS class II (10,11).

MXD was first developed as an oral agent medication for the treatment of hypertension. Topical solutions of MXD with two dose strengths (2% and 5%) were approved by FDA in 1991. Later, MXD has been indicated as an off-label drug to treat alopecia areata (AA) as well as to improve body hair growth in other areas including the eyebrows and beard (12).

Figure (1.2) Chemical structure of MXD (11).

1.5.1 MXD mechanism of action

MXD is a potent vasodilator that acts by opening the ATP-dependent potassium channel located in the smooth muscles of the peripheral arteries. This allows potassium efflux and leads to relaxation of smooth muscle. MXD is similar to hydralazine and diazoxide in producing arteriolar vasodilation with actually no action on the capacitance vessels (13).

The cytoplasmic unbound Ca^{2+} is primarily responsible for vascular smooth muscle contractility. The contractility is determined by two main pathways: the influx of Ca^{2+} through voltage-gated channels from the extracellular compartment, and secondly, from intracellular Ca^{2+} stores. Regarding the extracellular Ca^{2+} sources, Ca^{2+} entry is via the Ca^{2+} channel, which is activated by depolarization of the cell membrane followed by voltage channel opening. Many factors induce membrane depolarization like high concentrations of KCl or activation of the Ca^{2+} channels. For intracellular sources where Ca^{2+} is released mainly from the endogenous source, in specific from the endoplasmic reticulum after activation by extracellular agonists for example cholinergic or adrenergic agonists, depending on the tissue type like pilocarpine which is used as a cholinergic agonist. On the other hand, the opening of the K^+ channel causes membrane hyperpolarization followed by a blockage of the Ca^{2+} channel with subsequent muscle relaxation (14).

K^+ channels are the predominant path for ion conductance in the smooth muscle; thus, they largely determine membrane polarization and subsequent muscle contraction. Briefly, the opening of the channel leads to efflux of K^+ ion with membrane hyperpolarization and relaxation. On the contrary, blockage of the K^+ channel causes membrane depolarization with subsequent contraction. Thus, the presence of high concentration KCl results in smooth muscle contraction (15).

1.5.2 Hair follicle response to MXD

The exact mechanism by which MXD potentiates hair growth is not fully understood, but there are many mechanisms by which the drug exerts its effect and treats AGA. As mentioned early in this section that MXD is widely used topically for the treatment of AGA, it exerts its activity by opening potassium channels and inhibiting calcium entry, releasing nitric oxide, increasing blood flow to the hair follicles, and modifying the D2 and E 2 pathways of prostaglandins. It has the ability to extend the anagen phase in hair follicles, resulting in effective hair loss prevention (8).

MXD affects the hair follicles of androgen and non-androgen-dependent areas since the drug is considered a potent vasodilator and the drug's effect is independent on neither inhibition of 5 alpha-reductase nor hormonal factor (12)

1.5.3 MXD therapeutic use in AGA

Oral MXD is no longer used because it has potential side effects. However, topical MXD has extensively been used and it possesses comparable advantages to oral MXD (16). According to a meta-analysis study, it showed that topical MXD application at all concentrations provided a better response in comparison with the placebo group. The mean differences of 8.11 hairs/cm² associated with 2% MXD and 14.90 hairs/cm² associated with 5% MXD treatment compared to the placebo group. A 5-years follow up study conducted on 31 patients with AGA treated with 2% and 5% MXD, showed that peak hair regrowth occurred after 1 year (17).

Many clinical trials have been conducted on topical MXD at several concentrations to assess its efficacy. In men with AGA, MXD solution 5% showed better response than 2% and placebo group with a significant increase in the mean difference in hair density both in male and female (18,19). Nevertheless,

side effects such as headache and dermatitis were more common with 5%, therefore, 2% is preferred especially for women (20).

1.5.4 MXD adverse effect

The use of topical MXD is considered safe and it is currently available as over the counter drug. The adverse effects of topical MXD solution are limited to the scalp with no systemic side effects. Induced hair loss is considered a common side effect of MXD. The latter is commonly known as shedding, which occurs due to the quick effect of MXD in inducing hairs in the telogen phase to shed before beginning the anagen phase. The treatment with topical MXD solution requires long term application for getting benefits. This chronic use of MXD could develop contact dermatitis to MXD itself or a specific ingredient in the preparation. The most common complaint among MXD solution users is scalp pruritus, itching and/or scaling (21).

The incidence of these adverse effects is higher with 5% MXD solution than it was with the 2% solution. The 5% formulation contains more propylene glycol (PG) (50%) than the 2% formulation which contains only 30%, such a high concentration may be associated with a higher incidence of itching, dryness and erythema. For those patients who have an allergy to PG, it should be substituted by another vehicle such as butylene glycol, glycerin, or polysorbate (22,23).

Topical MXD can also induce hypertrichosis in areas other than the scalp like cheeks, temples, forehead and. The effect occurred due to contamination of these areas depending on the concentration used, it is usually more pronounced with 5% solution than with the lower concentration of 2%. Hypertrichosis occurs more commonly in women than in men where it affects 9% of females and only 1% of males with the topically applied MXD 5% solution. Fortunately, this side effect is reversible and resolves within 4-5 months after termination of treatment (24). The

usual daily dose of topical MXD is twice a day, however, the excessive application of high doses is associated with increased systemic uptake with the consequent more systemic side effect (25).

1.5.5 MXD topical preparations

Because of the drug's poor aqueous solubility, conventional marketed topical preparations of MXD, such as spray, solution, foam, shampoo, and gel in concentrations ranging from 1 to 5%, are currently formulated with organic solvents and co-solvents such as ethanol and PG. Long-term use of current organic solutions causes the formation of MXD crystals due to ethanol evaporation, which may result in many undesired side effects as those mentioned earlier which limit its usefulness in addition to the requirement of high doses (21,22).

Another major drawback to such preparations is the short contact time with the scalp. Since the suggested mechanism of increased hair growth is local vasodilation, thus, the shorter the contact time of the drug solution with the scalp, the more applications are required to obtain a clinical effect. As a result, there is a need to maximize the contact time during which the local drug concentration increases, resulting in enhancing vasodilation. Accordingly, huge efforts have been conducted to increase the contact time, enhance skin drug penetration to the scalp hair follicles and attain the controlled release of drug for a prolonged period which may help patients in reducing the frequency of application and improve patient compliance (26). Thus, it is necessary to develop an innovative topical drug delivery system that can overcome the limitations of conventional formulations using approaches to increase diffusivity and trans-follicular targeting by incorporation of MXD in nanocarrier for topical treatment of AGA (27).

There are many types of nanocarriers which include: solid lipid nanoparticles (SLNs), niosomes, liposomes, microemulsions, nanostructured lipid carriers (NLCs) etc. Among these different nanocarriers, nanoemulgel (NEG) has been suggested as the best topical preparation, which gains great interest as a drug nanocarrier that can improve skin permeation with prolonged effect at the site of application. Topical NEG can be prepared simply by adding a gelling agent to optimized nanoemulsion (NE) formulation and therefore the preparation shows the properties of both NE and gel (28).

1.6 Nanoemulsion (NE) as a topical delivery system

The outermost layer of the epidermis is the stratum corneum (SC). It forms a hydrophobic barrier that limits the absorption of drugs through the skin surface (29). The transdermal delivery vehicles should have the ability to deliver the drug to the surface of the skin at a constant rate and sufficient amount (30). One strategy that is employed to enhance drug permeation through the skin is the use of a nano-sized drug delivery system which increases the solubility and bioavailability of lipophilic drugs (31).

Nanoemulsion (NEs) are a transparent colloidal dispersion system consisting of a mixture of two immiscible liquids either oil-in-water (o/w) or water-in-oil (w/o), which are kinetically stable and stabilized by the use of the appropriate ratio of surfactant, with the mean droplet size less than 500 nm. The unique characteristics of NE with long term stability and no coalescence make it thermodynamically stable (32). The small droplets size of NE makes it clear, translucent that differs from the milky or white conventional emulsion and allowed higher capacity of drug loading (33).

The term NE is sometimes interchanged with submicron emulsion, but it should not be confused with microemulsion (ME). Despite having the same

droplet size, NE differs in structural aspects and long term thermodynamic stability (34). NE was reported as a novel transdermal delivery system and can be used for delivering both hydrophilic and hydrophobic drugs using water-in-oil (w/o) and oil-in-water (o/w) preparations, respectively (35). **Figure (1.3)** illustrates the various components of stable w/o and o/w NEs (36).

Figure (1.3) Different components of w/o and o/w NEs (36).

Several mechanisms have been proposed for enhanced transdermal delivery of drugs from NE. One of these suggested mechanisms is the components of NE such as surfactant that contains fatty acids or penetration enhancers that affect the integrity of SC, disrupts lipid bilayer, and increase their fluidity. Therefore, the resistance to the drug diffusion is reduced.

NE may also enhance skin absorption by the movement of drugs between their lipophilic and hydrophilic domains into the SC. This movement leads to a constant supply of drugs in the external phase. In certain circumstances, drugs can permeate through skin appendages (hair follicle, sebaceous gland and possibly sweat glands), due to the large surface area provided by the follicular infundibulum of hair follicles associated with reduced SC barrier thickness and width.

The hair follicle is a potential site for targeted drug delivery into the skin to treat certain conditions related to hair follicles such as alopecia. The presence of sebum in hair follicles and sweat ducts facilitate trans-follicular delivery of the NE (37). **Figure (1.4)** shows the different pathways of drug penetration through SC (32).

Figure (1.4) Schematic representation of pathways of skin penetration through SC (32).

1.7 Nanoemulgel (NEG) as a topical drug delivery system

Despite its many benefits, NE has issues with spreadability and skin retention due to its low viscosity (38). These drawbacks limit the therapeutic use of NE platforms for topical applications (39). The integration of NE in a gelling system has been proposed as a solution to this issue (40). Gels are produced by incorporating a colloidal solid particle network with large volumes of aqueous or hydro-alcoholic bases (41).

NEG formulation overcomes the drawbacks of both NE and hydrogel by combining both NE and gel properties. It is possible to introduce hydrophobic molecules into a hydrogel first by incorporating the compound into the oil phase

of a NE and then introducing it to the gel base (42). In addition, the gel matrix can control the rate of drug penetration into the different skin layers. On the other hand, the gelling system increases the viscosity of the NE; thus, it can be applied topically. Several biocompatible gelling agents have been reported, including carbomer 980, carbomer 940, carbomer 934, pluronic and xanthan gum, which have minimal interaction with surfactants and can adjust the viscosity of NEs (43). Due to their non-greasy, non-irritant, and better drug release properties, topical NEG can increase patient adherence (41). Because of the homogeneous behavior and consistency of the hydrogel matrix, NEG becomes a popular dosage form in recent years (44).

1.7.1 Components of topical NEG

Formulation of topical NEG requires a variety of materials such as oil/lipids, surfactants, co-surfactant and water that should be compatible with the skin. NEG formulation requires the inclusion of some special components such as polymers that are used as gelling agents, penetrations enhancers, preservatives, and antioxidants.

1.7.1.1 Aqueous phase

Most generally, distilled water (DW) is used as the aqueous phase in the formulation of NEG. This phase is responsible for the conversion of emulsion form into emulgel in the presence of a gelling agent (45).

1.7.1.2 Oils and lipids

The selection of oils and lipids for NE preparation is a very important parameter and usually, the amount of oils and lipid components used is based on the type of emulsion (commonly about 5-20% lipid used in cases of o/w emulsion) and the solubility of the drug that loaded in the formulation (36).

Physical and chemical properties of the oil phase, such as viscosity, water-solubility, density, polarity, refractive index and interfacial tension, as well as chemical stability, are among the factors that have an impact on the formation, stability and characteristics of NE (46). The oils and lipids which are approved to be used in the formulation of NE are classified according to chain length as long-chain triglycerides (LCTs), medium-chain triglycerides (MCTs) and short-chain triglycerides (SCTs). Fractions of oils and lipids that are derived from plant origins such as soybean oil, sesame oil, clove oil, cottonseed oil and rice bran oil are widely used either alone or as a mixture as an oil phase. D- α -Tocopherol (vitamin E), oleic acid and ethyl oleate have been used extensively in the preparation of NE (36).

Clove oil is also used as an oil phase in the formulation of NE. Clove oil is used to treat a variety of diseases. It has been shown to have a wide range of pharmacological bioactivities, including analgesic, antibacterial, antifungal, antiallergic, anti-inflammatory, anticarcinogenic, and antimutagenic properties. Numerous compounds have been found in clove oil, with eugenol (88.85%) being the phenolic principal ingredient responsible for the majority of the biological actions (47). Moreover, the presence of eugenol, which has an anti-androgenic effect and stimulates hair root feeding, makes it a good candidate for anti-hair loss formulation (48).

1.7.1.3 Surfactant

Surfactants are surface-active molecules with both hydrophilic and lipophilic domains (49). The surfactant's amphiphilic structure allows for the dispersion of two immiscible phases, reducing interfacial tension and resulting in a sufficiently stable film (50). They are readily adsorbed at the oil-water interface during the emulsification process, preventing the droplets from aggregating (51).

Surfactants are typically categorized using the hydrophilic-lipophilic balance (HLB) value, which is an empirical number on a scale ranging from 0 to 20. It depends on the contributions of the hydrophilic and lipophilic portions of the molecules. An HLB value of 0 for a non-ionic surfactant corresponds to a fully lipophilic molecule, whereas a value of 20 corresponds to a completely hydrophilic molecule (52). In general, intermediate-high HLB surfactants, ranging from 11 to 16, are preferred for the formulation of colloidal systems characterized by the dispersion of an oil phase in an aqueous phase (53). Surfactants are molecules that can improve permeation across the skin, which is thought to be due to their ability to reversibly attach to keratin filaments, destroy corneocytes and change the SC diffusion coefficient (54,55).

Non-ionic surfactants are preferred as the first choice because they are safe and widely tolerated for systemic absorption (56). Surfactants that are most popularly used are sucrose esters, sorbitan fatty acid esters, glycerol fatty acid esters (polyglycerols), polyoxyethylene sorbitan fatty acid esters (polysorbates) and polyoxyethylene ether (57). The polysorbates Tween 80[®] and Tween 20[®], which have been shown to offer stable formulations with or without the use of a co-surfactant, are the two most commonly used surfactants for the formulation of essential oil-based colloidal systems (58). Tween 20[®] and Tween 80[®] were compared for their effectiveness in achieving eugenol NEs in terms of droplet diameter and stability by Ghosh et al., Tween 80[®] was the most successful, although both had a significant impact on droplet size, size distribution, and polydispersity index (PDI) value (59).

1.7.1.4 Co-surfactant

A co-surfactant is a surface-active amphiphilic molecule that cannot stabilize an emulsion by itself due to the small size of the polar head. Instead, it aids in the

development of NEs by synergistically supporting surfactant activity. Short/medium-chain length alcohols are the most popular co-surfactants since they are small molecules of an amphiphilic nature, a hydrocarbon chain, and a hydroxyl group. They quickly disperse between the oil and water phases until they reach the interface (59). Alcohols can affect the solubility properties of the oil and water phases due to their partitioning between the two phases (60). Among this group of co-surfactants, ethanol is the most often used in the formulation of essential oils-based NE because it promotes the development of systems that can be easily diluted in the aqueous phase (61).

The surfactant/co-surfactant ratio is a critical element in determining phase properties, which are influenced by variations in surfactant and co-surfactant packing at the oil/water interface. As a result, fixed ratios cannot be established because they can vary depending on the surfactant, co-surfactant, and oil phase used. In this case, a formulation study is commonly used to determine the best qualitative-quantitative composition (58).

The pseudoternary phase diagram is the most widely used screening method. This technique was used to determine the accurate concentration range for the development of nanoemulsion utilizing the water titration method. Different diagrams can be constructed by varying the surfactant/co-surfactant (S_{mix}) volume ratio (62). R. Thapa et al., for example, used the aqueous titration method to construct pseudoternary phase diagrams for the achievement of diflunisal and niflumic acid NE by changing the percentages of the aqueous phase, surfactant: co-surfactant mixture and oil phase (63).

1.7.1.5 Gelling agents

One of the most important components of NEG is the gelling agent, which gives the formulation its texture. There are two kinds of gelling agents: natural and synthetic (64).

The effect of a gelling agent on the rate of drug released from emulgel has been investigated. It has been discovered that the concentration of gelling agent and the amount of drug released have an inverse relationship. The prepared emulgel exhibited non-Newtonian shear thinning behavior and variable viscosity that changed depending on the concentration and type of gelling agent. Stability tests under a wide range of conditions (centrifugation, temperature cycle test, or one-year storage) revealed that formulations with a low level of carbopol or a mixture of two gelling agents have greater stability than other formulations (65).

Gel forming agents can be classified into (66)

- A.** Natural polymers like collagen, gelatin, alginic acid and tragacanth.
- B.** Semisynthetic polymers such as carboxymethyl cellulose, methylcellulose and hydroxypropyl methylcellulose.
- C.** Synthetic polymers like carbomer and poloxamer
- D.** Inorganic materials like Aluminum hydroxide and bentonite
- E.** Surfactants such as cetosteryl alcohol.

1.7.1.5.1 Carbomers

Carbomers are acrylic acid polymers with a high molecular weight that are cross-linked with allyl sucrose or allyl ethers of pentaerythritol. Different grades of carbomer are available depending on the degree of cross-linking and manufacturing requirements, such as carbopol 934 (lowest cross-linking density), carbopol 981 (intermediate cross-linking density) and carbopol 940 (highest cross-linking density) (67).

Carbopols, in general, have a high water sorption capacity. When carbopol is exposed to a pH range of 4.0 to 6.0, they swell in water to 1000 times their original volume and 10 times their original diameter, forming a gel (68). It is thus possible to jellify carbopol particles in certain semi-polar liquids or mixtures of these liquids with water by using organic amines as a neutralizing agent.

1.7.1.6 Other components

Other additives could be used as preservatives and antioxidants. To prevent the growth of microorganisms, water-based systems should typically have a preservative agent. The commonly used preservatives are methylparaben, propylparaben, benzalkonium chloride, benzoic acid, etc. Antioxidants prevent oxidation from degrading the formulation's components. Antioxidants including butylated hydroxyl toluene, ascorbyl palmitate, and butylated hydroxyl anisole are very useful in preventing oxidation problems (69).

1.7.2 Preparation of NE

NE is a non-equilibrium system of structured liquids that requires a lot of energy, surfactant, or both to fabricate (69). NEs may be made spontaneously by blending the compositions and lowering the interfacial tension between the oil/water interfaces, or by introducing high energy into the heterogeneous mixture. Thus, high-energy and low-energy emulsification processes may be used to create a thermodynamically stable NE (70).

1.7.2.1 High-energy method

Since NE droplet sizes usually range from 5 to 500 nm, achieving this size requires a lot of mechanical energy. The high energy input for fabrication can be accomplished using a variety of techniques, including high-pressure homogenizers, ultrasound generators, and high-speed homogenizers (71,72). The

use of low emulsifier concentrations is the most important benefit of high energy mediated NE formulation (73).

High-energy techniques are based on a two-step process that starts with the development of an emulsion by mechanical stirring, with oil droplets in the micron range. The second step involves breaking down large oil droplets into small ones using high-energy mechanical equipment to convert the coarse emulsion into a NE (58).

1.7.2.1.1 Ultrasonication

With the aid of a sonicator probe, the coarse emulsion is converted into desired nano-sized emulsion droplets. The sonicator probe generates sound waves with a frequency of more than 20 kHz. The high-intensity sound waves shatter the coarse emulsion into nano-sized droplets (5-500nm). To reduce the droplet size to desirable limits, different types of probes with various dimensions are available. The scale of the droplet is determined by the input power and time for sonication, as well as the probe type (74).

1.7.2.1.2 High-pressure homogenization

In this technique, numerous forces such as hydraulic shear, severe turbulence, and cavitation, are frequently utilized for the development of NEs. The surfactants and co-surfactants are passed through a small orifice of a piston homogenizer under high pressure (500-5000 psi) to generate NEs. The problem of coalescence that would occur can be solved by incorporating excess surfactants into the mixture. High-pressure homogenization is a highly effective method and a cost-effective technology that can be used on both a small and a large scale to produce NEs of extremely low particle size (up to 1 nm).

The droplet size varies according to homogenization cycles, and dispersed and continuous phase viscosities. The main drawbacks include the consumption of a lot of energy and raising the temperature during the processing, which may lead to component deterioration. This approach works well for a NE that has 20% or less oil content since a high volume of oil in the formulation decreases the method's productivity (75).

1.7.2.1.3 High-speed homogenization (rotor-stator high-speed stirrer)

High-speed homogenizers are commonly used in industry for emulsification, dispersion, and comminution. They are simple to mount in existing vessels and tanks and are inexpensive. Rotor-stator processes are often the emulsification method of preference in many manufacturing industries. Many studies prove that it is possible to produce nanoscale droplets by using rotor-stator processes. However, this necessitates the precise selection of method and formulation parameters. A range of rotor-stator emulsification devices are widely available from different manufacturers in a variety of structural styles. Each of these designs share one thing in common, one part of the system is mobile and the other is stationary (76).

Early studies suggested that rotor-stator systems could produce emulsions with mean droplet sizes in the micrometer range. P. Scholz et al. found that a high-speed stirring method is a very efficient method in producing NEs. The process develops physically stable NEs with a size around 135 nm and a low polydispersity index (77).

1.7.2.2 Low-energy method

In comparison to high-energy methods, the fabrication of NEs using a low-energy emulsification method requires less energy. This method includes the use of the systems' internal chemical energy and it just requires a moderate stirring to

produce NEs. Phase inversion emulsification and spontaneous emulsification are two low-energy emulsification methods (78).

1.7.2.2.1 Spontaneous emulsification

Spontaneous emulsification is one of the most practical methods of NE preparation. It involves two liquid phases, one aqueous and another phase is organic. Water miscible components such as solvent, surfactant, and co-surfactant are moved from the organic phase to the aqueous phase. The process begins with the introduction of an organic phase, such as oil and surfactant, into an aqueous phase, which consists of water and co-surfactant. The rapid migration of water-miscible components into the aqueous phase causes massive turbulence at the phase interface and increases the oil-water interfacial area. This results in the spontaneous formation of small oil droplets (79).

1.7.2.2.2 Phase Inversion composition (PIC)

The phase inversion composition (PIC) approach is a more advanced type of spontaneous emulsification. This process, unlike the high-energy method, develops NEs at ambient temperature and does not require energy-intensive equipment. At room temperature, a laboratory-scale magnetic stirrer is utilized to mix oil and surfactant while water is introduced drop by drop. Then, as the volume of water is increased, a w/o NE is generated first, followed by an o/w NE at the inversion point, all without consuming substantial energy as shown in **Figure (1.5)** (79).

Figure (1.5) Formation of NE by phase inversion composition (79).

1.7.2.2.3 Phase inversion temperature technique (PIT)

In the PIT technique, a change in the temperature reverses spontaneous surfactant curvature. Non-ionic surfactants, such as polyethoxylated surfactants, undergo dehydration in polyoxyethylene (POE) groups, which makes them more lipophilic and causes surfactants to change curvature. Therefore, the phase inversion takes place and the NE developed (78).

1.7.3 preparation of NEG

NEG development is a multi-step process in which a formed NE is combined with a suitable gel base. The required polymer is dissolved in purified water with continuous stirring through a mechanical device while adjusting the pH until a gel is formed (69).

After preparing the NE and the gelling agent, the two are mixed by continuous stirring until a NEG is formed. With the aid of various polymeric gelling agents, a liquefied form of water in oil (w/o) or oil in water (o/w) NE is transformed into thick and semisolid NEG (69).

1.8 Literature review on NEG formulation

Topical NEG of diflunisal (DIF) and solubility enhanced diflunisal (DIF-IC) have been formulated and characterized by Bashir and his colleagues for enhancing its topical anti-inflammatory activity. DIF and DIF-IC NE formulations were developed using eucalyptus oil as the oil phase, Tween 80[®] as a surfactant, transcuto-P as a co-surfactant and combined with three different gelling agents: carboxymethylcellulose sodium (CMC- Na), sodium alginate (Na-ALG), and xanthan gum (XG). An in-vitro skin permeability study of solubility enhanced diflunisal DIF-IC-loaded NEG formulations was considerably higher than that of the diflunisal DIF-loaded NEG. Enhanced solubility diflunisal (DIF-IC) NEG formulation with xanthan gum (XG) resulted in enhancing the in-vivo anti-inflammatory effect (80).

E. Yeo et al. developed and evaluated a tocotrienol-rich naringenin NEG for topical treatment of diabetes-related chronic wounds. In this study, a combination of capryol 90 and tocotrienols as an oil phase, solutol HS15 as a surfactant, transcuto P as a co-surfactant and carbopol 934 and 940 were selected as gelling agents. Within 24-hours, the in-vitro release of naringenin in phosphate buffer saline (PBS) demonstrated a sustained release profile up to a maximum of $74.62 \pm 4.54\%$ from the formulated NEG (NG1). The release from NE was significantly greater ($89.17 \pm 2.87\%$), possibly owing to the lack of polymer covering the dispersed oil droplets (81).

In another work, the efficacy of brucine-loaded NEG for transdermal delivery was tested by M. Abdallah et al., for effective anti-inflammatory and anti-nociceptive effects of brucine (BRU). The formulations used myrrh oil as an oil phase, Tween 80[®] as the surfactant, PG as co-surfactant and ethanol as a solvent.

In this study, 1% w/w sodium carboxymethyl cellulose was used as a gelling agent. High-speed homogenizer and then ultrasonication methods were used in the preparation of NE. Several formulations (BRU-gel, emulgel, and NEG) were prepared. Brucine loaded NEG exhibited a much higher cumulative drug release than the other formulations. When compared to brucine loaded gel or emulgel, ex-vivo drug permeation of the NEG formulation across the skin of rats demonstrated enhanced drug permeation and greater transdermal delivery. Furthermore, NEG formulation has the most effective anti-inflammatory effect. Additionally, when applied to rat skin, brucine loaded NEG evoked no edema nor erythema, according to a skin irritation test (82).

Topical delivery of finasteride NEG for treatment of AGA has been investigated by U. Deepak et al., and they attempted to enhance drug penetration through the skin, improve in-vivo response and increase contact time with the skin. NE was prepared using an oily solution containing soy lecithin, vitamin E oil, chloroform and cholesterol and the water phase was composed of polyethylene glycol 600 and DW. The results showed that the cumulative drug release of finasteride was 94.77% and 73.39% in 24 hours from NEG and solution, respectively. Permeation via the skin is limited, with around 30% permeation in 24 hours. The macroscopic inspection revealed an enhancement in hair growth with improving hair diameter in the treated group compared to the testosterone-treated group (83).

M. Elmataeeshy et al., have prepared a novel topical NEG containing terbinafine to increase its aqueous solubility and enhance transdermal permeability and antifungal efficacy. In the formulation of NE, peceol was used as the oil phase, Tween 80[®] as a surfactant and propanol as a co-solvent. The optimum NE formulation content was added to the carbopol 940 gel base, forming the final

NEG. In comparison to the commercial emulgel, terbinafine skin penetration from all the resulting NEG formulae was considerably enhanced. The in-vivo antifungal activity of the NEG formula was superior to that of the commercial emulgel for the treatment of Candida infection (84).

According to Hussain et al., a range of NEG formulations of amphotericin B (0.1%), using sefsol-218 oil, Tween 80[®], transcitol-P and carbopol gel (0.5% w/w) were prepared. NEG achieved the maximum percutaneous permeation flux for amphotericin-B (18.09 mg/cm²/h), compared to NE (15.74 mg/cm²/h) and drug solution (4.59 mg/cm²/h). The NEG exhibited a sustained amphotericin-B drug release profile through the in-vitro drug release study (85).

1.9 Literature review on MXD formulation using nanotechnology

S. Cardoso et al. developed a topical NE containing MXD for improving follicular penetration and controlling drug delivery in the treatment of alopecia areata. High-energy ultrasonication was used to produce the NE. Clove oil was used as the oil phase while Kolliphor[®] P188 was chosen as the surfactant. The prepared NE showed both low droplet size and low polydispersity and long term stability. Moreover, the optimized NEs showed controlled drug release 2 times more efficiently than the control ethanolic solution. Compared to typical ethanol-based solutions, MXD skin penetration from NEs was increased by more than 9 times. MXD NEs permeated hair follicles more than 26 times more efficiently than a control sample, according to follicular accumulation and permeation studies (27).

Self-assembled nanovesicles of oleic acid and phosphatidylcholine were studied by K. Pawan et al., to investigate the follicular delivery of MXD. The controlled release of MXD from the vesicular gel was demonstrated through an

in-vitro drug release study. In skin permeability and deposition examinations, the resulting MXD vesicular gel (0.2%) exceeded MXD lotion (2%) in terms of MXD deposition in the SC and residual skin, with augmentation ratios of 3.0 and 4.0, respectively. MXD deposition inside the hair follicles was 10-fold greater with the vesicular gel compared to the control (86).

E. Abd et al., developed a NE of MXD for better skin delivery with oleic acid or eucalyptol oil as the oil phase and penetration enhancer. They found that MXD penetration from NEs was higher than penetration of the control solution. The NE system produced significantly higher fluxes compared to control and this could be attributed to the improvements in both MXD SC solubility and skin diffusion of NE systems (87).

W. Wenxi, et al., developed MXD-loaded nanostructured lipid carriers (NLCs) using oleic acid as a liquid lipid and stearic acid as a solid lipid for improving skin penetration of minoxidil. They were found that the NLCs released MXD faster than the MXD loaded SLNs. MXD-loaded NLCs showed a more prominent permeation and retention profile than MXD-loaded SLNs in an in-vitro skin permeation study. Furthermore, this study showed that no erythema was seen after the delivery of minoxidil NLCs (88).

Aim of the study

Conventional MXD solution, which is formulated using an organic solvent, suffers from short contact time with the scalp, poor drug penetration, and high dose requirements, which are related to a range of side effects.

We hypothesize that the preparation of nanoemulgel of minoxidil will prolong the contact time with scalp, improve penetration and enhance pharmaco-dynamic efficacy with the lower side effects.

The present study aims to prepare an o/w nanoemulsion-based gel drug delivery system of MXD

(Chapter Tow)

Experimental

Work

2 Experimental work

2.1 Materials

Materials used in this study are listed in **Table (2.1)**

Table (2.1) Materials used in the study.

Material	Supplier
1,2-Propylene glycol	Merck [®] , Germany
Absolute ethanol (analytical grade)	Scharlab S.L. [®] , Spain
Calcium chloride	Sigma-Aldrich, USA
Carbopol 934 polymer	HIMEDIA [®] , India
Castor oil	Lobachemie [®] lab reagents and fine chemicals, India
Clove oil	SAC [®] - S.AMDEN and COMPANY 95 and 96/E, Pakistan
Glucose	Merck [®] , Germany
Magnesium Sulfate	Merck [®] , Germany
MXD pure powder	Pharmaroya [®] pharmaceutical cosmetic industry, Turkey
MXD spray (Hair grow 2%)	Dar Aldawa pharmaceutical industry, Jordan

Oleic acid	Sigma-Aldrich, USA
Pilocarpine eye drop (Apicarpin 2%) [®]	Amman pharmaceutical industry, Jordan
Polyoxyethylene sorbitan mono-oleate Tween 80 [®] (synthesis grade)	Scharlab S.L. [®] , Spain
potassium chloride	Scharlab S.L. [®] , Spain
Potassium dihydrogen phosphate	Scharlab S.L. [®] , Spain
Sodium bicarbonate	Sigma-Aldrich, USA
Sodium chloride	Scharlab S.L. [®] , Spain
sodium hydroxide	Scharlab S.L. [®] , Spain
Triethanol amine	AVONCHEM [®] limited, UK

2.2 Instruments

Instruments used in the study are listed in **Table (2.2)**

Table (2.2) Instruments used in the study.

Instrument	Manufacturer
Centrifuge	labofuge A [®] HERAEUS SEPTech, Germany
Dialysis membrane (Mw CO 8000-14000 D)	special products laboratory, USA

Digital conductivity tester	Senz μ siemen , trans instrument , Singapore
Digital pH meter	EcoTestr pH 2, Singapore
Dissolution apparatus	Copley scientific, UK
Electronic balance	ADAM [®] equipment, USA
FTIR Spectrometer	BRUKER, USA
Franz diffusion cell	Permegear, inc., USA
Heating oven	Genlab limited [®] , UK
High-speed Homogenizer mixer	Fisher Scientific PowerGen 125, USA
Hot-plate stirrer	Labnet International, Inc. Mexico
Magnetic stirrer	Isotemp [®] fisher scientific, Korea
Melting point apparatus	Stuart Scientific, UK
Membrane filter (0.2 μ m)	Chromafil AO-20/25 [®] , Germany
Membrane filter (0.45 μ m)	Chromafil AO-20/25 [®] , Germany
Micropipette (10-1000 μ l)	Accumax lab. Device, India
Micropipette (5-50 μ l)	Dragon lab, China
Particle size analyzer	Anton Paar Litesizer 500 instrument, Austria

Tissue Organ bath	Radnoti [®] Adinstrument organ bath, USA
Transmission electron microscope (TEM)	Zeiss EM10C, Germany
Ultrasonic bath (Sonicator)	Powersonic 410 HWASHIN ultrasonic cleaner R, Korea
UV-visible spectrophotometer	Labomed, Inc. USA
Viscometer	Brookfield DV-II Viscometer, USA
Water distillator	Daihan Labtech CO. LTD, Korea

2.3 Methods

2.3.1 Characterization of MXD

2.3.1.1 Determination of drug melting point

The melting point of MXD powder was measured using melting point apparatus by sealed capillary glass tube method. A sufficient amount of MXD powder was placed in a small glass capillary tube with one end closed. The tube was put in the melting point apparatus, and the temperature was progressively raised until the powder completely melted; the temperature was recorded at this moment (89).

2.3.1.2 Determination of maximum wavelength absorption (λ max)

MXD primary stock solution (500 μ g/ml) was prepared by dissolving 25 mg of MXD in a 50 ml phosphate buffer solution pH 7.4. From this stock solution, secondary stock solution (100 μ g/ml) was prepared by transferring 10 ml of primary stock solution to 50 ml volumetric flask and then scanned

spectrophotometrically using UV-Visible double beam spectrophotometer in a range from 200 nm to 400 nm to determine the maximum absorbance (90).

Phosphate buffer solution pH 7.4 was prepared according to United States Pharmacopeia by the following procedure (91):

- a. 0.2 M Monobasic potassium phosphate; 27.22g/l
- b. 0.2 M sodium hydroxide; 8 g/l

50 ml of the monobasic potassium phosphate solution was placed in a 200 ml volumetric flask, then 39.1 ml of the sodium hydroxide solution was added and the volume was completed with DW to 200 ml. Finally, the pH was measured using a digital pH meter.

2.3.1.3 Establishing a calibration curve of MXD

The calibration curve of MXD in phosphate buffer solution pH 7.4 was built up by preparing serial dilutions of the MXD from a secondary stock solution. Solutions with different concentrations (2, 4, 6, 8, 10, 12, 14, 16, 18 and 20 $\mu\text{g/ml}$) were prepared then analyzed spectrophotometrically for MXD at its λ_{max} (288nm). To establish a UV calibration curve model, the measured absorbance was plotted against the concentrations (90).

2.3.1.4 Fourier Transform Infrared Spectroscopy (FTIR)

Samples of MXD powder were analyzed by FTIR spectroscopy in the wavelength range of 4000-400 cm^{-1} . Small amount of the sample was placed to form a thin film on the window of the FTIR spectrometer (90).

2.3.2 Selection of oil phase

2.3.2.1 Solubility study of MXD in different oils

The preliminary solubility of MXD was measured in different oils. To conduct the test, clove oil, castor oil, and oleic acid were used. Then the selection of the best oil was made based on visual inspection by observing the clarity and transparency of the resulting solutions. Five milligrams of MXD was added to 5 mL of each of the oils listed before. The systems were then placed in an ultrasonic bath for 15 min to allow faster solubilization, and solubility was determined visually after 24 hours. The aforementioned technique was repeated for the oil that was able to enhance MXD solubilization until drug precipitation was observed for each system. The oil with the highest solubility for MXD was chosen (27).

2.3.2.2 Determination of emulsifying efficiency of surfactant in different oils

To select the oil phase, precisely, another preliminary test was conducted based on visual observation of maximum emulsification efficiency of the surfactant on different oils. The procedure involved using an aqueous titration method, which includes the addition of the oil phase drop by drop to a 10% v/v aqueous solution of Tween 80[®]. After each addition of the oil phase, the mixtures in the beakers were gently mixed with a magnetic stirrer and allowed to equilibrate until the mixture of the two phases remained clear and transparent. Then, the oil phase was gradually added to the surfactant solution until turbidity appeared. After 24 hours, the sample mixture was visually inspected for signs of phase separation. It was possible to see which oil has the best emulsification stability in a 10% aqueous surfactant solution (27).

2.3.3 Construction of pseudoternary phase diagram (phase behavior study)

To obtain the NE areas and the precise concentrations of NE components, a pseudoternary phase diagram was constructed using an aqueous titration method. Based on the literature review and preliminary solubility studies, clove oil was selected as an oil phase, Tween 80[®] was selected as surfactant and ethanol was selected as a co-surfactant. In addition, DW and propylene glycol (PG) were used as an aqueous phase and co-solvent, respectively.

Tween 80[®] and ethanol were used at different volume ratios to form what is known as Smix (surfactant: co-surfactant). Different ratios of Smix (1:1, 1:2, 1:3 and 2:1) were studied for the development of NEs. For each phase diagram, clove oil and Smix were thoroughly mixed in separate beakers at various volume ratios (1: 9, 2: 8, 3: 7, 4: 6, 5: 5, 6: 4, 7: 3, 8: 2, and 9: 1). The solvent system (DW/PG at a ratio of 8.5:1.5) was then added in a dropwise manner and titrated slowly at ambient temperature. After each addition of the aqueous phase, the mixtures in the beakers were gently shaken for 2 min using a magnetic stirrer and allowed to equilibrate. The point at which the physical state of the mixture was changed from transparent to turbid was visually determined and recorded as volume. CHEMIX (cxse 900) software was used to present the data as a triangle graph. Each axis in the triangle represents one of the components of the NE (oil phase, aqueous phase and Smix ratio) (80).

2.3.4 Preparation of MXD-loaded NE formulae

The MXD-loaded NE was prepared by a low-energy method; then a high-speed homogenization technique was employed. The pseudoternary phase diagram was used to determine suitable volume ratios of oil and Smix, and eight different formulae were prepared as shown in **Table (2.3)** based on the NE clear area of each diagram. These volume ratios were predicted to produce an o/w NE

due to the decreased oil-to-water ratio. In these NE systems, physical conditions and transparency were inspected.

One hundred milligrams of MXD was accurately weighed as required for the preparation of 10 grams of the formula, and it was dissolved in the Smix at its predetermined Tween 80[®] and ethanol ratios by sonication for 20 min in an ultrasonic bath. Then, the clove oil was added to the mixture and the whole mixture was stirred for 5 min at 700 rpm using a magnetic stirrer. After that a specified volume of the solvent system (DW+PG) was dropped with continuous stirring until a homogenous clear and transparent NE was obtained (84). The schematic representation of the preparation of NE was shown in **Figure (2.1)**. Finally, the prepared NE was subjected to high-speed homogenization to achieve a stable NE, and it was carried out by using a high-speed homogenizer in a discontinuous mode. A liquid of 10 ml of each prepared formula is processed by applying 3 consecutive cycles of 5 min on and 5 min off at 25000 rpm (92).

Table (2.3) Compositions of different MXD-loaded NEs (the red box refer to the selected ratio as per section 3.6).

% w/w of a component of NE							
No.	Formula code	Smix (S:Co-S) ratio	Smix (Tween80 : Ethanol)	Oil (Clove oil)	Co-solvent (Propylene glycol)	Distilled water (DW)	Drug (MXD)
1	NE-A1	1:1	40	5	8.25	46.75	1
2	NE-A2	1:2	40	5	8.25	46.75	1
3	NE-A3	1:3	40	5	8.25	46.75	1
4	NE-A4	2:1	40	5	8.2	46.75	1
5	NE-A 5	1:2	40	8	7.8	44.2	1
6	NE-A 6	1:2	40	10	7.5	42.5	1
7	NE-A7	1:2	35	5	9	51	1
8	NE-A8	1:2	45	5	7.5	42.5	1

Figure (2.1) The schematic representation of the preparation of NE. In the first step, MXD was accurately weighed and it was dissolved in the Smix. In the third step, the clove oil was added to the mixture. Finally, the solvent system was dropped until a clear NE was obtained.

2.3.5 Characterization of MXD-loaded NE

2.3.5.1 Visual Inspection

The color, appearance and homogeneity of the prepared NE were all visually checked (93).

2.3.5.2 Measurement of pH

The pH of all prepared NE formulae was measured using a pH meter. One milliliter of each formula was diluted ten times with 10 ml DW (1:10). Then pH was measured. All measurements were done in triplicate (94).

2.3.5.3 Measurement of electrical conductivity

To determine the type of the NE continuous phase or signs of phase inversion, the electrical conductivity was measured. One milliliter of the prepared NE formulae was diluted ten times with DW (1:10) and then the conductivity was measured using a digital conductivity tester (95).

2.3.5.4 Measurement of light transmittance

The percentage of light transmittance (T%) was measured for all prepared NEs formulae. One milliliter of each formula was diluted 10 times with DW and T% was determined using a UV-Visible spectrophotometer at 630 nm and keeping DW as blank.

The T% was calculated using the following equation (96):

$$A = 2 - \log T\% \dots\dots\dots \text{Equation (2.1)}$$

Where:

A: absorbance

T%: transmittance percentage.

2.3.5.5 Droplet size and size distribution of the prepared NE

The droplet size and droplet size distribution of all prepared NEs formulae were measured by a dynamic light scattering technique (DLS) using a particle size analyzer (Litesizer 500, Anton Paar, Austria). The prepared formulae were placed in the omega cuvette (Mat. No. 155765) at 25 °C and the measurement angle was set in an automatic mode. Droplet size was presented as a mean hydrodynamic diameter (HDD) and droplet size distribution was presented as a polydispersity index (PDI) percentage. All measurements were conducted in triplicate (97).

2.3.5.6 Measurement of zeta potential (ZP)

The zeta potential of all prepared NEs formulae was measured by an electrophoretic light scattering technique (ELS) using a zeta potential analyzer (Litesizer 500, Anton Paar, Austria) by measuring particle speed in the presence of an electric field. Using the Omega Cuvette, each sample was placed in a cuvette and then its tip is closed and put into a measurement chamber. The test was conducted at 25 °C and was done in triplicate (97).

2.3.5.7 Assay of drug content

The drug content of all prepared formulae was determined by taking 0.5 ml of each sample and suitably diluted in a phosphate buffer solution pH 7.4 to the required concentrations. MXD concentration was determined by measuring the absorbance using a UV-visible spectrophotometer at the selected maximum wavelength (λ max) and the test was conducted in triplicate (26,98). By using the following equation, the drug content was calculated:

$$\text{Drug content} = \frac{\text{Analyzed content (test)}}{\text{Theoretical content(standard)}} * 100 \dots \dots \dots \text{Equation (2.2)}$$

2.3.5.8 Determination of entrapment efficiency

The entrapment efficiency of MXD-loaded NE formulae was determined by the separation of untrapped drug of each of the prepared formulae using the ultrafiltration method by 0.2 μ m syringe filters. Then, these samples were diluted in phosphate buffer solution pH 7.4 to the required concentrations and the absorbance of MXD were determined by UV-visible spectrophotometer at the selected λ max. (The test was done in triplicate) (99).

EE% was calculated using the following equation:

$$\text{EE (\%)} = \frac{\text{Quantity of API entrapped}}{\text{Total quantity of API added}} * 100 \dots \dots \dots \text{Equation (2.3)}$$

2.3.5.9 Thermodynamic stability study

Stability testing was conducted as recommended by the International Conference on Harmonization (ICH) of technical requirements for registration of pharmaceuticals for human use. According to ICH, Iraq is located in the climate zone III region, where alternate cooling and heating cycles were used in the stability studies. The NE formulae were kept in amber glass vials to protect products from oxidation. Different thermodynamic stability tests were conducted on the resulting NE formulae as explained in the following sections.

2.3.5.9.1 Heating-cooling cycle

The NE formulae were subjected to six cooling and heating cycles at temperatures ranging from (4 to 45 °C, RH 70%), with each temperature being kept for 48 hours. After that, the samples were examined for precipitation or phase separation.

2.3.5.9.2 Centrifugation

The formulae which remained stable after the heating-cooling cycle were centrifuged for 30 min at 3500 rpm. After centrifugation, formulae that did not show any phase separation were subjected to a freeze-thaw cycle.

2.3.5.9.3 Freeze-thaw cycle

To check if there is phase separation, the selected formulae were subjected to three freeze-thaw cycles between -21 °C and +25 °C for 48 h at each temperature (100).

2.3.6 Selection of optimized formula

The selection of optimized formula among the eight prepared MXD-loaded NE formulae was conducted according to the results of characterization studies such as droplet size, polydispersity index and zeta potential. The selected formula

then is subjected to further studies such as in-vitro drug release, transmission electron microscopy (TEM) and pharmaco-dynamics study. Furthermore, different NEG formulae were prepared by adding carbopol 934 at different concentrations into the selected optimized NE formula.

2.3.6.1 Transmission electron microscopy (TEM)

The morphology and size of the optimized MXD-loaded NE formula were characterized by transmission electron microscopy (TEM, Zeiss EM10C, Germany). The optimized formula was diluted by DW 100 times. One drop of diluted sample was transferred on a film of carbon-coated copper grid mesh 300, dried for 1 h at room temperature and then measured by TEM at 100 kV (101). This test was conducted in Iran because this facility is not available in Mosul.

2.3.7 Preparation of MXD-loaded NEG formulae (MXD-loaded NEG)

2.3.7.1 Preparation of gel

Carbopol 934 was selected as the gelling agent. Carbopol 934 solutions at different concentrations (1% w/v, 2% w/v and 3%w/v) were prepared by dissolving the required weight of carbopol 934 in 10 ml DW with a constant stirring at moderate speed using a magnetic stirrer. After getting a complete dispersion, the dispersed solution is kept in a dark place for 24 hours to allow the polymer to be fully hydrated and to remove any entrapped air bubbles. Then, the pH was adjusted to 5.5 by adding a few drops of triethanolamine (TEA) and the resulting gel was clear and transparent (102).

2.3.7.2 Incorporation of gel phase with optimized MXD-loaded NE formula

Three different MXD-loaded NEG formulae were prepared, as shown in **Table (2.4)**, by incorporating the optimized MXD-loaded NE formula with a previously prepared gel at different concentrations. The mixing was in a ratio of 9:1 of NE to

gel with a constant stirring at optimum speed using a magnetic stirrer until uniform and homogeneous NEG was obtained. The steps of preparation of NEG is shown in **Figure (2.2)**.

Table (2.4) Compositions of different MXD-Loaded NEG.

% w/w of a component of NEG							
Formula code	Smix (S:CO-S) ratio	Smix (Tween80 :Ethanol)	Oil (Clove oil)	Co-solvent (Propylene glycol)	Distilled water (DW)	Drug (MXD)	Carbopol 934
NEG-A2x	1:2	40	5	8.25	46.75	1	0.1
NEG-A2y	1:2	40	5	8.25	46.75	1	0.2
NEG-A2z	1:2	40	5	8.25	46.75	1	0.3

Figure (2.2) Preparation of NEG.

2.3.8 Characterization of MXD-Loaded NEG

2.3.8.1 Visual inspection

The color, appearance and homogeneity of the prepared NE were all visually checked.

2.3.8.2 Measurement of pH

Accurately weighed 1 g of MXD-loaded NEG formulae were diluted ten times with 10 ml DW (1:10). Then the pH was determined using a digital pH meter (98).

2.3.8.3 Measurement of spreadability

The spreadability test was conducted on all MXD-loaded NEG formulae using a wooden block and glass slide apparatus. A homemade apparatus which is demonstrated in **Figure (2.3)** was utilized, and the device is made up of a wooden block with a pulley attached to one end. Two glass slides of the same dimensions were employed in this device, and spreadability was determined based on the "slip" and "drag" properties of the NEG. Two grams of each prepared formula were placed on the surface of a glass slide that was already fixed on the wooden block. The NEG samples were then sandwiched between this slide and an upper glass slide. A weight of 100 g was placed on the surface of the upper slide for 5 min to expel air and to produce a consistent thin film. The upper glass plate was then dragged with a 20 g weight using a string attached to the hook and the time (in seconds), which was needed for moving the upper slide 7.5 cm was recorded. A shorter interval indicates a faster spreadability (102).

Spreadability (S) was calculated by the following equation.

$$S = \frac{M * L}{T} \dots\dots\dots \text{Equation (2.4)}$$

Where:

S = spreadability

M = weight tied to upper slide (g),

L = length of glass slide (cm),

T = time taken by the slide to move the distance (sec.)

Figure (2.3) A homemade wooden block and glass slide apparatus to measure spreadability.

2.3.8.4 Measurement of viscosity

The viscosity of the developed NEG formulae was tested using Brookfield DV-II viscometer using spindle cone plate number CP-41z, which was immersed in each sample of the prepared formulae and rotated at a different speed (0.1, 1 and 5 RPM). The viscosity was measured at 22.5 ± 2 °C in triplicate (93).

2.3.8.5 In-vitro drug release

The in-vitro drug release test was conducted using a USP dissolution apparatus type II (paddle apparatus) at a rotation speed of 50 rpm and temperature maintained at 37 ± 0.5 °C using a dialysis bag (Molecular cut off: 12000-14000 D). The Dialysis bags were soaked in phosphate buffer solution pH 7.4 at room temperature and kept overnight before use. The photographic image of the paddle type dissolution apparatus that used in the study was shown in **Figure (2.4)**. The in-vitro drug release was studied for MXD-loaded NEG formulae, optimized MXD-loaded NE, standard alcoholic solution 1% and MXD marketed solution (Hairgrow[®] 2%, Dar aldawa, Jordan).

The tested samples were placed in dialysis bags. The bags are then closed from both ends, attached to the dissolution apparatus paddle using a cotton thread and immersed completely in 200 ml phosphate buffer solution pH 7.4 (see figure 2.7). Aliquots of 5 ml were withdrawn at intervals of 5 min, 15 min, 0.5, 1, 2, 3, 4, 6 and 7 hours and suitably diluted. Each aspirated sample was compensated by an equal volume of phosphate buffer pH 7.4. The samples were examined by a UV-visible spectrophotometer at the λ max of the drug 288nm. The percentage of cumulative drug release was calculated and plotted against time (103). (Each test was performed in triplicate).

Figure (2.4) Photographic image of paddle apparatus used for in-vitro drug release of MXD (red box refer to the dialysis bags that used in the study).

2.3.8.5.1 Mathematical modelling of drug release

Various kinetic models and equations were used to determine the release kinetic of MXD in which the cumulative release data was fitted into zero-order kinetics, first-order kinetics, Higuchi model and Korsmeyer and Peppas's model. The kinetic model is chosen based on the highest correlation coefficient (r^2) (104).

For **the zero-order model**, the following equation was used to depict drug release from a dosage form, according to pharmacokinetic principles:

$$C_t = C_0 - K_0 t \dots\dots\dots \text{Equation (2.5)}$$

Where:

C_t is the amount of drug released at time t ,

C_0 is the initial concentration of drug at time $t=0$,

K_0 is the zero-order rate constant.

To study the drug release kinetics, data of cumulative drug release % is plotted against time.

While for **the first-order kinetic**, the following equation was used:

$$\log C = \log C_0 - K_1 t / 2.303 \dots\dots\dots \text{Equation (2.6)}$$

Where:

K_1 is the first-order rate equation expressed in time^{-1} or per hour,

C_0 is the initial concentration of the drug,

C is the percent of drug remaining at time t .

to analyze drug release kinetics, log percent of drug remaining plotted against time, with the slope of the plot indicating the first-order rate constant.

For **Higuchi Model**, we used:

$$Q = KH \times t^{1/2} \dots\dots\dots \text{Equation (2.7)}$$

Where:

KH is the Higuchi dissolution constant.

To estimate drug release kinetics, the resulting data were plotted as cumulative percentage drug release versus square root of time.

Finally, for **Korsmeyer and Peppas's model**, the following equation was used

$$\log(M_t/M_\infty) = \log K_{kp} + n \log t \dots\dots\dots \text{Equation (2.8)}$$

M_t/M_∞ is a fraction of drug released at time t ,

M_t is the amount of drug released in time t ,

M_∞ is the amount of drug released after time ∞ ,

n is the diffusional exponent or drug release exponent,

K_{kp} is the Korsmeyer release rate constant.

To study release kinetics a graph is plotted between log cumulative % drug release $\log(M_t/M_\infty)$ versus log time ($\log t$).

2.3.8.6 Ex-vivo permeation study

Ex-vivo skin permeation study protocol was approved by the institutional animal care and use committee at the college of veterinary medicine/ University of Mosul with approval number (UM.VET.2021.004) (see **appendix-3**). The study was conducted using a Franz diffusion cell with an effective diffusional area of 0.64 cm² and a volume of 5 ml receiver chamber capacity. Skin from Swiss albino rat weighing 200 ±10 gm was used in this study and full thickness of fresh skin was surgically removed from the abdomen and subcutaneous tissue was surgically removed then the hair was removed by hair clipper.

Finally, the skin was immersed and well hydrated in phosphate buffer solution pH 7.4. The skin sample was placed in the Franz diffusion cell and fixed between the donor and receiver chambers, with the SC facing the donor chamber then the receiver chamber filled with phosphate buffer solution pH 7.4. and kept at constant

temperature 37 ± 0.5 °C with continuous stirring at 260 rpm for 24 hours using a hot plate magnetic stirrer.

The study was conducted on the optimized MXD-loaded NEG formula and marketed solution (Hairgrow[®] 2%, Dar aldawa, Jordan), and tested samples were introduced directly onto the skin in the donor chamber. Samples of 0.3 ml were withdrawn at intervals of 0.5, 1, 2, 4, 6, 8 and 24 hours, and each removal was replaced by equal volumes of phosphate buffer solution pH 7.4. Samples were adequately diluted and examined by a UV-visible spectrophotometer at the λ max of the drug (105).

2.3.8.6.1 Permeation parameters analysis

The cumulative amount of MXD that permeated per square centimeter through the abdominal skin rat (Q , $\mu\text{g}/\text{cm}^2$) was measured and plotted versus time. The permeation rate (flux) at steady state (J_{ss}) was measured from the slope of the plot which is generated by plotting the cumulative amount of MXD permeated per unit area versus time at steady-state conditions. The permeability coefficient (K_p) was measured by dividing the permeation rate at a steady state of MXD over the initial drug concentration, which was applied to the donor compartment (C_o) as shown in the equation given below:

$$K_p = J_{ss} / C_o \dots\dots\dots \text{Equation (2.9)}$$

Where:

K_p : is the permeability coefficient

J_{ss} : steady-state flux

C_o : initial concentration of MXD in the donor compartment.

Enhancement ratio (Er) was calculated by dividing the Kp of the optimized MXD-loaded NEG formula by the Kp of the marketed solution as control and calculated according to the following equation (106):

$$\text{Er} = \text{Kp of formulation} / \text{kp of control} \dots\dots\dots \text{Equation (2.10)}$$

2.3.8.7 Pharmacodynamics study

2.3.8.7.1 Preparation of Krebs-Henseleit buffer solution

Krebs-Henseleit buffer solution was prepared and stored as previously reported method by Minasian et al., using the following concentration of the chemicals (NaCl 118 mM, KCl 4.8 mM, CaCl₂.H₂O 1.3 mM, NaHCO₃ 25.0 mM, KH₂PO₄ 1.2 mM, MgSO₄.7H₂O, glucose 11.1 mM) (107).

2.3.8.7.2 Tissue selection

The selection of the proper tissue is considered the cornerstone of conducting the pharmacodynamics study via organ bath system. Different tissues were selected as models to examine the relaxation effect of MXD. First, trials were conducted on coronary segments isolated from sheep hearts. Then, MXD relaxation was also examined on aortic vessels isolated from rats. However, the study lastly was conducted on sheep bladder segment, the latter was robust tissue, it could be easily being contracted by the cholinergic agent, pilocarpine, unlike other tissues which show no response to such contractile agent.

2.3.8.7.3 Tissue Preparation

Sheep bladder segments were used to characterize the effects of MXD. Bladder tissue from sheep of both sexes was obtained from a local slaughter shop. The tissue was then kept in an icebox containing a physiological solution, Krebs-Henseleit buffer until it was delivered to the laboratory for further dissection. The bladder tissue is finely dissected to be cleaned and to remove any connective

tissues and fat that may physically interfere with in-vitro tissue contraction. A photographic image of sheep bladder tissue dissection and preparation for the experiment was shown in **Figure (2.5)**

The bladder was then divided into 5mm-length segments and suspended between two metal hooks in 50 ml organ baths. The upper hook was attached to a transducer sensitive to force tension while another hook was connected to the base of the bath. Photographic representation of metal hooks that are used in organ bath is shown in **Figure (2.6)**. The baths were filled with 50 ml of a physiological solution, Krebs-Henseleit, the solution temperature was set at 37 °C by a circulating water bath and continuously aerated with oxygen. The transducer is connected to the data acquisition system via an amplifier (labscribe)[®] (108).

Figure (2.5) Photographic image of sheep bladder tissue dissection and preparation for the experiment.

Figure (2.6) Photographic image of organ bath. (A) A fifty ml organ bath that filled with Krebs-Henseleit buffer solution, (B) The 2 metal hooks that used to connect the bladder tissue and fixed inside the organ bath (red color refer to upper metal hook linked to string and fixed to the base of the bath and yellow color refer to lower metal hook that fixed into the metal arm).

2.3.8.7.4 Isometric tension recording

Tissues were first stretched to 10 g, this tension was determined from previous experiments, then it was left to relax to the baseline for about 30 min. A photographic image of the organ bath final set up and isometric tension is demonstrated in **Figure (2.7)**. The stretching will keep the tissue under tension and simulate the in-vivo conditions. Once baseline tension was obtained, two additions of 60 mM KCl was added to the bath to induce tissue depolarization and examine the contractility of the tissue by inducing membrane depolarization.

After each KCl addition, the tissue was left for about 15min to obtain maximum depolarization, then the baths were washed out with normal Krebs, left for another 20 min for basal tone stabilization, then followed by cumulative addition of pilocarpine 38.4 μM to stimulate tissue contraction to about 50% of KCl contraction before the addition of MXD solution. The pharmaco-dynamic study was conducted on the optimized MXD-loaded NE formula NE-A2 and compared with MXD marketed solution (Hairgrow[®] 2%, Dar aldawa, Jordan). An Accurate 25 μL of marketed solution and 50 μL of prepared NE formula, which is equal to 47.8 μM were introduced directly onto each channel, separately. The extent of relaxation was measured for a further 2 hours. The above-mentioned experimental method was repeated thrice for each treatment (108).

Figure (2.7) The photographic image represents the organ bath whole set-up. (A) The isometric tension digital transducer records the tension that applied on the tissue (B) the whole set-up of the organ bath during running the experiment.

2.3.8.8 Fourier Transform Infrared Spectroscopy (FTIR) of MXD-loaded NEG

By using the FTIR technique, a compatibility study was conducted for MXD and other ingredients in the NEG formula to detect any chemical interactions. The spectrum was determined for pure MXD and MXD-loaded NEG formulas (90).

2.3.8.9 Stability study at different storage conditions

Stability experiments were carried out to check for any physical or chemical changes in the formulation during storage. The optimized MXD-loaded NEG formula was kept in an amber glass vial. The formula was exposed to three different temperatures: 6 ± 2 °C (the refrigerator), 25 ± 2 °C (the room temperature), and 40 ± 2 °C /75 % RH (a stress condition) for 90 days. The formula was tested for changes in color, homogeneity, pH and electrical conductivity after 1, 2, and 3 months (109).

2.3.8.10 Statistical Analysis

Every experiment was carried out and repeated three times ($n=3$). Data were analyzed and expressed using GraphPad Prism 9.2.0. and Microsoft Office Excel 2016. Numeric data were expressed as (Mean \pm SD). One-way, two-way analysis ANOVA followed by Tukey's test for Post-Hoc Analysis and unpaired t-test were used when applicable for comparing values of the mean in the various groups when the values were within the normal distribution. The statistical significance was ascertained at ($P \leq 0.05$). *** indicated a high significance when ($p \leq 0.001$).

(Chapter Three)

Results

And

Discussion

3 Results and discussion

3.1 Characterization of MXD

3.1.1 Determination of drug melting point

The MXD was melted at about 248 °C. This result demonstrates the high purity of MXD powder and comes in agreement with documented references (11).

3.1.2 Determination of maximum wavelength absorption (λ max)

Scanning the diluted solutions of MXD in phosphate buffer solution pH 7.4 by UV-visible spectrophotometer was conducted at the range of 200-400 nm and the result was shown in **Figure (3.1)**. MXD exhibited three absorptions maxima at 229, 260 and 288 nm. The selected λ max was 288 nm, which is selected by similar previous work (90). Interestingly, the selected range of concentrations that are used in this study demonstrated linearity when measured at this peak.

Figure (3.1) UV spectrum of MXD in phosphate buffer solution pH 7.4.

3.1.3 Establishing a Calibration Curve of MXD

The calibration curve of diluted MXD solution in phosphate buffer solution pH 7.4 was shown in **Figure (3.2)**. The calibration curve was built up by plotting the absorbance versus concentration. A straight line was obtained with a high r^2 (0.9995), which means that the curve obeys Beer-Lambert law within the selected range of concentrations. Thus, this method can be considered a good method for MXD quantification.

Figure (3.2) Calibration curve of MXD in phosphate buffer solution pH 7.4. (n=2)

3.1.4 Fourier Transform Infrared Spectroscopy (FTIR)

The measured FTIR spectrum of pure MXD powder is shown in **Figure (3.3)** and it shares the same distinctive peaks of the FTIR spectrum of MXD that is presented in the reference and the spectral band assignments were found within the range as recorded by reference (90,110), see **Table (3.1)**.

Table (3.1) FTIR Spectrum band assignments of pure MXD.

No	IR bands γ cm^{-1}	Assignment groups (Stretching bands)
1	3408.82, 3270.18	N-H (NH_2)
2	3036.41	C-H aromatic
3	2931.59, 2847.47	C-H cyclic aliphatic (CH_2)
4	1603.69	C=N conjugated group
5	1219.35	N-O

C:\Alla Pharmaceuticals\mxd.2	mxd	Instrument type and / or accessory	10/03/2020
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Figure (3.3) FTIR spectrum of pure MXD powder (red box indicates the spectral band assignment of MXD powder).

3.2 Selection of oil phase

3.2.1 Solubility study of MXD in different oils

All the excipients selected to be used in the formulations are safe and are non-irritant to the skin as well as they are pharmaceutically acceptable. The selection of NE formulation components should be very precise because not all excipients could produce a stable NE. To generate a stable formulation, the components should have optimum drug solubility as well as good miscibility with each other. Drug loading is considered as one of the important factors in the selection of components and in determining a formulation approach.

Three different oils were selected depending on the screening of available literatures, and then the oil phase was chosen after conducting two simple visual tests. The first one is the solubility of MXD in different oils. The results are shown in **Table (3.2)**. The results indicated that the solubility of MXD in various oils was in the following descending order: Oleic acid > clove oil > castor oil. The results showed that oleic acid and clove oil have the highest solubilization capacity of MXD.

Table (3.2) Saturation solubility of MXD in different oils.

Oil type	Solubility mg/ml
Castor oil	1
Clove oil	17
Oleic acid	18

Before determining the emulsification efficiency of surfactant in different oils, the selection of the remaining components was made. Based on the available solubility profile of MXD, Tween 80[®], ethanol and PG were selected as surfactant, co-surfactant and co-solvent, respectively for NE formulation (26,111,112).

Tween 80[®], which is a non-ionic surfactant, is safe and non-irritant compared with the ionic surfactant. Tween 80[®] is a hydrophilic surfactant with an HLB value equal to 15 and it is preferred for the formulation of o/w NEs due to the easy formation of the droplet (113). Ethanol was selected as a co-surfactant due to its partitioning between both phases. Ethanol increases the miscibility of the aqueous and oily phases and lowers interfacial tension. In addition, ethanol enhances the mobility of the hydrocarbon tail, allowing more oil entry into this region (114). To enhance MXD solubility in the NE system and enable drug loading of 1% (w/v), PG was used as a co-solvent in the ratio of 15% (v/v) in the formulation and was added to the aqueous phase. This percentage of PG was selected depending on the previous work of A. Saberi et al., who concluded that using PG as a co-solvent had a significant effect on the development and stability of NEs (115).

The type and amount of co-solvent present influenced the initial droplet size and optical clarity of the NEs. Although higher concentrations of co-solvent in the aqueous phase could produce small droplets, Saberi reported that NEs were susceptible to coalescence during storage, particularly at elevated temperatures (115). Accordingly, a 15% (v/v) PG was selected in this study to get better droplet size and maximum stability.

3.2.2 Determination of emulsifying efficiency of surfactant in different oils

The selected oil phase for NE formulation should have the ability to be dispersed efficiently into fine droplets in 10% (v/v) Tween 80[®] solution without

any signs of phase separation. The results are shown in **Figure (3.4)** demonstrate that the Tween 80[®] solution has the good capacity to disperse clove oil in water without any visible sign of phase separation, hence clove oil was chosen as the oil phase for the fabrication of MXD-loaded NE. The results also demonstrated that the solubility of various amounts of different oils in 10% (v/v) Tween 80[®] solution was found in the following descending order: Clove oil > oleic acid > castor oil. A 10% (v/v) Tween 80[®] solution can disperse up to 28.43 ±0.42% of clove oil, 16.37 ±0.38% of oleic acid and 9.17 ±0.35% of castor oil.

The results revealed that a 10% (v/v) Tween 80[®] solution could disperse a large amount of clove oil in coarse macroemulsion. This does not mean that the same amount of clove oil could be added to a stable NE, given that smaller droplet sizes indicate a significant increase in the oil/water interface. Such a formulation would necessitate a high proportion of surfactants, possibly with the inclusion of co-surfactants (27).

Tween 80[®] shows the greatest emulsification for clove oil, and this might be due to the high emulsification efficiency of Tween 80[®] on eugenol, which is the major component in clove oil. Our finding is consistent with results reported by Nagaraju et al., who found that using Tween 80[®] in preparation of clove oil based NE achieved a long term stable NE, due to the high interaction of Tween 80[®] with oil droplets. Tween 80[®] inhibited particle coalescence by causing repulsive interactions between oil droplets at the interfacial layer. Tween 80[®] is made up of an oleate chain with 18 carbon atoms and one unsaturated bond. This bond might be responsible for forming an interaction with clove oil, which also included unsaturated bonds (116).

Figure (3.4) Solubility of different oils in 10% Tween 80[®] solution. Data are expressed as mean \pm SD, *# P \leq 0.05.

3.3 Construction of pseudoternary phase diagram (phase behavior study)

In the absence of MXD, pseudoternary phase diagrams were constructed to identify the NE region (monophase area) and to optimize the concentration of oil, surfactant, and co-surfactant in NE formulations by using Tween 80[®] as a surfactant, ethanol as a co-surfactant, and PG and DW as the solvent. Four diagrams were constructed using the aqueous titration method at ambient temperature, and by varying the volume ratio of surfactant to co-surfactant (S: CO-S) in what is called Smix and the diagrams named (1:1, 1:2, 1:3 and 2:1).

The shaded area in the pseudoternary phase plot represents the area of NEs, whereas the unshaded area shows the emulsion area. The plot with a larger shaded region suggests that the produced NEs have ideal nano-emulsifying efficiency and

good interaction between the Smix, oil, and aqueous phase (84). Tween 80[®] has an HLB value of 15, indicating that they are hydrophilic surfactants. These surfactants are more soluble in the aqueous phase, favoring the formation of o/w NEs according to Bancroft's rule, which mentions that the phase in which the surfactant is more soluble reflects the continuous phase and determines the type of the resulting NE whether it is (o/w) or (w/o) (117).

The pseudoternary phase diagram plots for different Smix volume ratios of 1:1, 1:2, 1:3 and 2:1 are shown in **Figure (3.5)**. According to the results obtained from each diagram, the largest shaded area (NE area) is shown in diagram 2:1. This result might be due to an increase in the concentration of surfactant to co-surfactant in Smix 2:1 relative to 1:1, which causes a great improvement in oil solubilization. Furthermore, at Smix 1:2 and 1:3 ratios, an increase in co-surfactant concentration with a corresponding decrease in surfactant concentration resulted in a reduction in the NE area. This result is similar to a previously reported work by A. Khames et al., who prepared eplerenone NE as an oral drug delivery system with improved bioavailability (118).

The decrease in NE area in diagrams 1:2 and 1:3 could be attributed to the low concentration of Tween 80[®], which decreases micelle formation and, as a result, reduces NE solubilization activity. Tween 80[®] stabilizes the NEs by lowering the system's interfacial tension, limiting physical contact between the droplets, and reducing the chance of coalescence (119). The Smix ratio has been found to have a considerable impact on the phase behavior of NE systems.

According to these results, the MXD-loaded NE formulae were prepared from the NE shaded areas that are shown in all the diagrams. (see **figure (3.5)**).

(A)

(B)

(C)

(D)

Figure (3.5) Pseudoternary phase diagrams. The diagrams showed (o/w) NE (shaded area) regions of clove oil (oil), Tween 80[®] (surfactant), ethanol (co-surfactant) at different Smix ratios: (A) Smix 1:1, (B) Smix 2:1, (C) Smix 1:2 and (D) Smix1:3 at ambient temperature.

3.4 Preparation of MXD-loaded NE formulae

A huge number of formulations can be prepared from the shaded areas of clear NE regions of all pseudoternary phase diagrams. However, eight formulae loaded with 1% (w/v) of MXD were prepared only and stored for further evaluation. To obtain the optimum formula, two preparation steps were conducted where different formulae were prepared using different Smix ratios (S: Co-S) and being characterized to identify the best ratio selection of NE preparation (See **Table 2.3**). Once a proper Smix ratio was selected, oil and surfactant concentrations were manipulated to obtain the best concentration. The first point was selected from each diagram and four formulae were prepared named NE-A1 (Smix ratio 1:1), NE-A2 (Smix ratio 1:2), NE-A3 (Smix ratio 1:3) and NE-A4 (Smix ratio (2:1)). The best selected diagram is then subjected to change in the concentrations of both oil and Smix. Accordingly, further four formulae were prepared named NE-A5, NE-A6, NE-A7, and NE-A8.

Besides using suitable emulsifiers to reduce the interfacial tension and stabilize the NE, a high-energy emulsification method is also required to produce a stable NE. It was reported that the preparation of a stable NE with small droplet size and low polydispersity index could be achieved by varying the concentrations of Smix and mechanical energy using a high-speed homogenizer. Then, we selected 25000 rpm homogenization speed for 5 min in 3 consecutive cycles. Similar work was conducted by T. Adak et al., who studied the effect of the rotational speed of a high-speed homogenizer on thermodynamic stability. They pointed out that increasing the homogenization speed results in the production of a thermodynamically stable NE (92).

3.5 Characterization of MXD-loaded NE

3.5.1 Visual Inspection

Visual inspection indicated that all the produced eight formulae had a clear and homogenous yellow color with no phase separation or drug precipitation as shown in **Table (3.3)** and **Figure (3.6)**. The prepared NE formulae should be kept in dark amber glass vials to avoid the oxidation of clove oil. When the formula did not store properly, the color become slightly darker (dark yellow). Such a color shift was previously described by Barradas et al., who noticed a color change in clove oil-based NE followed by a decrease in pH, which they linked to the generation of small chain organic acids as a result of oxidation of numerous components in clove oil, such as aliphatic unsaturated alcohols and aldehydes. (120).

Table (3.3) Visual inspection of prepared MXD-loaded NE formulae.

Visual inspection of prepared NE			
Formula code	Color	Homogeneity	Appearance
NE-A1	Light yellow	Homogenous	Clear
NE-A2			
NE-A3			
NE-A4			
NE-A5			
NE-A6			
NE-A7			
NE-A8			

Figure (3.6) The image of the prepared formulae. It shows clear, homogeneous yellowish color NE.

3.5.2 Measurement of pH

The pH values of the prepared MXD-loaded NE formulae were shown in **Table (3.4)**. The pH values were found to be between 7.2 and 7.4. These values indicated that all NE formulae have neutral pH and could be applied safely to the skin without any irritation due to physiological compatibility with the skin pH (112).

3.5.3 Measurement of electrical conductivity

Electrical conductivity is also called phase analysis, which refers to the ability of any material to conduct an electrical charge. This test determines the type of NE, whether it is o/w or w/o. For o/w emulsion, the conductance value is greater than 10 $\mu\text{S}/\text{cm}$ while for w/o emulsion, the conductance value is less than 10 $\mu\text{S}/\text{cm}$ (121). According to the results presented in **Table (3.4)**, all the prepared NE formulae were of the o/w type, because all eight formulae had conductivity values of more than 10 $\mu\text{S}/\text{cm}$, ranging from $25.67 \pm 2.66 \mu\text{S}/\text{cm}$ for NE-A3 to $43.17 \pm 2.04 \mu\text{S}/\text{cm}$ for NE-A4. It was noticed that the conductivity value for formula NE-A3 was the least among the other formulae due to the higher ratio of

ethanol in the Smix. In comparison, the NE-A4 formula has a higher value of conductivity, which might be due to the lowest ratio of ethanol in the Smix. The explanation behind the significant difference ($P \leq 0.05$) between NE-A3 and NE-A4 formulae might be that increasing the concentration of ethanol will cause more hydrogen bond interactions with water, which leads to a reduction of the ions speed in the solution, and consequently lowers the electrical conductivity (122).

3.5.4 Measurement of light transmittance

The transmittance percentage of NE demonstrates the system's transparency. The values of transmittance of all eight formulae are shown in **Table (3.4)**. The percentage of transmittance of NEs was in the range of $98.10 \pm 0.57\%$ to $99.19 \pm 0.4\%$. This result reveals that all formulae were clear, transparent, and easily transmit the light due to the resulting nano-size droplets; thus, transmittance percentage values in **Table (3.4)** were closer to 100%, resulting in greater transparency confirming the formation of NE (123).

Table (3.4) pH, conductivity and transmittance% of the prepared NE formulae. Data are expressed as mean \pm SD, * $P \leq 0.05$. (n=3)

Formula code	pH	Conductivity μ S/cm	Transmittance%
NE-A1	$7.4 \pm 0.1^*$	39.17 ± 1.33	$99.18 \pm 0.6^*$
NE-A2	$7.4 \pm 0.04^*$	$31.67 \pm 2.88^*$	$99.17 \pm 0.2^*$
NE-A3	7.3 ± 0.1	25.67 ± 2.66	98.78 ± 0.9
NE-A4	7.2 ± 0.05	43.17 ± 2.04	$99.19 \pm 0.4^*$
NE-A5	7.3 ± 0.06	37.2 ± 1.72	98.62 ± 0.13
NE-A6	7.2 ± 0.06	38.5 ± 2.07	98.10 ± 0.57
NE-A7	$7.4 \pm 0.011^*$	38.0 ± 1.7	98.77 ± 0.25
NE-A8	$7.4 \pm 0.08^*$	40 ± 0.9	98.95 ± 0.47

3.5.5 Measurement of droplet size and polydispersity index of the prepared NE formulae

The average NE hydrodynamic diameter (HDD) is essential in formulation development because it influences the drug release behavior from NE droplets. It has previously been observed that the smaller the HDD of NE droplets, the faster the medication permeates through the epidermal layers (124). To accomplish desirable transfollicular penetration, the optimum HDD for follicular delivery was found to be between 20 and 200nm (125).

Measurement of the HDD of the MXD-loaded NE was conducted and the experimental results are shown in **Figure (3.7)**. The results show that the mean HDD for all formulae ranged from 14.62 ± 1.36 nm for the NE-A2 formula (**see the full report in appendix-1**) to 512.3 ± 150.53 nm for NE-A4. Huge differences in HDD were noticed between different formulae and this could be attributed to a change in different parameters such as S_{mix} ratio, oil concentration, and S_{mix} concentration.

To study the effect of S_{mix} ratio on HDD, a comparison was made between NE-A1, NE-A2, NE-A3 and NE-A4, where the concentration of oil and co-solvent were constant. **Figure (3.7) (i)** showed that NE-A1, NE-A2, and NE-A3 formulae are in nanometric size except for NE-A4. In addition, it was pointed out that the NE-A2 formula with S_{mix} ratio (1:2), achieved the lowest HDD, which is statistically different ($P \leq 0.05$) from other formulae. The small mean HDD in NE-A2 may be attributed to the penetration of the co-surfactant molecules into the surfactant film. This may minimize the surface of the interfacial tension, lower the radius of curvature of droplets and produce transparent systems (126).

The results showed that NE-A4 has the largest HDD and this may be due to a change in the ratio of S_{mix} from (1:2) to (2:1). By increasing the Tween 80®

concentration in relation to ethanol, the mean HDD increased significantly from 14.62 ± 1.36 nm to 512.3 ± 150.53 nm ($P \leq 0.05$). Droplet size was increased as surfactant concentration increased, possibly due to the depletion-flocculation mechanism of adsorbed surfactant. As surfactant concentration rises, it forms micelles in the continuous phase rather than orienting them on particle surfaces. This results in moving the continuous phase between some droplets and finally depleting them. As a result, aggregation occurs, and the HDD increases (127).

On the other hand, to study the effect of oil concentration on HDD, a comparison was made between NE-A2, NE-A5 and NE-A6 formulae. It was observed in the results, which are presented in **Figure (3.7) (ii)** that the NE-A2 formula with a lower concentration of clove oil than NE-A5 and NE-A6, has a significantly smaller average HDD ($P \leq 0.05$) (14.62 ± 1.36 nm). It was elaborated that increasing the oil concentration to 8% (v/v) in formula NE-A5 produces large HDD (171.03 ± 20.28 nm). A further increment of essential clove oil concentration from 8% to 10% (v/v) in formula NE-A6, generated NEs with significantly high HDDs (198.50 ± 97.44 nm) ($P \leq 0.05$). This implies that the larger the oil content, the larger the mean HDD. These findings were consistent with the results of Y. Yuan et al., who found that an increase in the concentration of oil phase of the NE results in big HDD. This effect is due to the expansion of oil droplets in the NE and might also be due to the concurrent reduction in the Smix ratio in relation to oil concentration (128).

In contrast, a comparison was performed between NE-A2, NE-A7, and NE-A8 to examine the Influence of Smix concentration on HDD. **Figure (3.7) (iii)** demonstrated that the NE-A2 formula has an optimum Smix concentration of 40% (v/v). By reducing the Smix concentration to 35% (v/v) in formula NE-A7, the mean HDD was significantly increased from 14.62 ± 1.36 nm to 118.86 ± 35.71 nm

($P \leq 0.05$). When the emulsifier concentration at the interfacial layer between oil-water is insufficient to completely cover the surface of the drops, coalescence and flocculation of droplets occur and the size of the droplets is increased (121).

When the concentration of Smix was increased from 40% to 45% (v/v), as in formula NE-A8, the mean HDD significantly increased from 14.62 ± 1.36 nm to 272.53 ± 84.68 nm ($P \leq 0.05$). This result was in opposition to what is reported by Ghai et al., who found that increasing Smix concentration reduces the mean HDD since a high emulsifier concentration makes the interfacial film condense and stable (124). The reason behind that result is possibly due to the depletion-flocculation mechanism of adsorbed surfactant as mentioned previously.

Figure (3.7) Hydrodynamic diameter (HDD) for the eight formulae. (i) HDD for formulae with different Smix ratios, (ii) HDD for formulae with different concentrations of oil, (iii) HDD for formulae with different concentrations of Smix were separately shown. Data are expressed as mean \pm SD, *\$# is statistically significant compared to group A2 at $P \leq 0.05$.

The polydispersity index (PDI) measures the homogeneity of the nano-sized droplets. PDI ranges between 0.0 and 1.0. The closer the PDI to zero, the more homogeneous distribution the nano-sized globules are (129). **Figure (3.8)** represents the results of the PDI of all the prepared MXD-loaded NEs. All the prepared formulae had a PDI in the range of 0.20 to 0.29, which represent good results. **Figure (3.8) (i)** showed no statistical differences ($P \leq 0.05$) among NE-A1, NE-A2, NE-A3 and NE-A4. In addition, **Figure (3.8) (iii)** showed no statistical differences ($P \leq 0.05$) among NE-A2, NE-A7 and NE-A8. On the other hand, **Figure (3.8) (ii)** revealed a significant difference in NE-A2 in comparison with NE-A5 and NE-A6 ($P \leq 0.05$). As mentioned before, when oil concentration increases, the chance of coalescence and expansion of oil also increases. In all cases, PDI was found to be less than 0.3, which indicates a homogeneous distribution of nano-sized droplets within the NE and ensure the stability of the system (130).

Figure (3.8) Polydispersity index (PDI) of the eight formulae. (i) The PDI for formulae with different Smix ratios, (ii) PDI for formulae with different concentrations of oil, (iii) PDI for formulae with different concentrations of Smix. Data expressed as mean \pm SD, *# $P \leq 0.05$.

The droplet size distribution analysis of the MXD-loaded NE formulae is represented in **Figure (3.9)**. It was found that only formula NE-A2 and formula NE-A3 have a mono-modal distribution with a single peak, which indicates a homogeneous droplet distribution and less liability for stability problems. However, the other formulae have bimodal and multimodal distributions with two or three peaks, which means the presence of ultimately aggregated droplets. These multimodal and bimodal distributions are most likely caused by oil droplet flocculation, which results in larger droplet size. This could encourage the coalescence of small droplets into larger ones, which reduces the stability and dispersion of NE. Indeed, the mean droplet size **Figure (3.7)** and polydispersity index **Figure (3.8)** could be implemented together with the size distribution analysis to explore the change in particle size distribution behavior (131).

Figure (3.9) Droplet size distribution of all the prepared NE formulae (The different colors represent the repeats of the reading of each formula). (The figure will continue in the next 2 pages).

A3

A4

A5

A6

A7

A8

Figure (3.9) Droplet size distribution of all the prepared NE formulae (The different colors represent the repeats of the reading of each formula).

3.5.6 Measurement of zeta potential

Zeta potential is an essential characteristic that describes the NE system's stability. An acceptable zeta potential value prevents aggregation and coalescence of NE during storage because it provides a sufficient degree of repulsion between neighboring dispersed particles with similar charges. The zeta potential value may be used to identify charge magnitude at the surface of droplets. Formulae having a zeta potential range equal to or greater than ± 30 mV are considered electrically stable systems (132).

The values of zeta potential of all formulae were presented in **Figure (3.10)** and **Figure (3.11)**. The values of zeta potential in all the prepared NE were negatively charged. This could be attributed to the presence of anionic groups of fatty acids and glycols, which are presented in the clove oil and PG (133). The presence of a negative charge on the surface of NE droplets encourages them to penetrate the skin (134). A similar finding was observed by Khurana et al., who

developed stable negatively charged meloxicam loaded NE gel containing caprylic acid as an oil phase (38).

The obtained results showed that values of zeta potential ranged from -7.77 ± 0.81 mV to -0.6 ± 0.1 mV, which are lower than previously reported electrostatic stabilization values. Formulae NE-A1, NE-A2 and NE-A3 have higher zeta potential values than the remaining formulae (**see the full report in appendix-2**), which have zeta potential values approaching zero. Although the values of zeta potential of prepared NE formulae were found to be low, these NE could be considered stable. The neutral character of clove oil based NE, which was produced from Tween80, was reflected in these near-zero results (135).

It is noteworthy to mention that Tween 80[®] has a large molecular weight, and it acts through steric stabilization rather than electrostatic stabilization. Values of merely about ± 20 mV or much lower can provide enough stabilization. The use of non-ionic surfactant, Tween 80[®], could contribute to the stability of emulsions although they have low zeta potential values. These non-ionic surfactants adhere onto nanoscale droplets and, while reducing zeta potentials, they maintain stability in o/w NEs by forming a hydrated layer on the lipophilic particle (136). **Figure (3.10)** demonstrated that there is no clear relationship between the measured zeta potential for formula prepared using different concentrations of oil or different concentrations of Smix. This comes in accordance with the results obtained by Nallamolu et al., who determined that the zeta potential value was not a straightforward function of a single component, but rather entailed several complicated interacting factors (137).

Figure (3.10) Zeta potential (ZP) represents the eight formulae. (i) ZP for formulae of different Smix ratios (ii) ZP for formulae with different concentrations of oil (iii) ZP for formulae with different concentrations of Smix. Data are expressed as mean \pm SD, *\$#@

$P \leq 0.05$.

Figure (3.11) Zeta potential values of the prepared NE formulae. (The figure will continue in the next 2 pages).

A3

A4

A5

A6

A7

A8

Figure (3.11) Zeta potential values of the prepared NE formulae.

3.5.7 Assay of drug content

The drug content results of the eight MXD-loaded NE formulae were acceptable and range between $99.03 \pm 0.79\%$ and $99.66 \pm 0.32\%$ as shown in **Table (3.5)**. The high uniform drug content indicated that all prepared formulae were homogenous with no drug precipitation. This would be attributed to entrapping the MXD in the oil phase. The greater drug content means little drug loss across various stages of formulation development (83). To determine whether MXD was entrapped in the oil phase or was only solubilized in the continuous or external aqueous phase, an entrapment efficiency test was conducted.

Table (3.5) Drug content % of the prepared NE formulae (mean \pm SD, n=3).

Formula code	Drug content %
NE-A1	99.77 \pm1.50
NE-A2	99.19 \pm1.05
NE-A3	99.20 \pm2.41
NE-A4	99.43 \pm2.21
NE-A5	99.33 \pm1.75
NE-A6	98.76 \pm1.37
NE-A7	99.70 \pm0.30
NE-A8	99.90 \pm2.85
* statistically significant at level $P \leq 0.05$.	

3.5.8 Determination of entrapment efficiency

The amount of drug entrapped or encapsulated is referred to as entrapment efficiency. The entrapment occurs due to the hydrophobic interaction between drugs and oil droplets (138). The result is shown in **Figure (3.12)** depicts the percentage drug encapsulation efficiency of all MXD-loaded NE formulae. It has been found that the actual amount of MXD entrapped is different, ranging from 95.2 \pm 0.84% to 85.92 \pm 0.54% with the drug entrapment varying by up to 9.12% between the formulations. The entrapped fraction of MXD was potentially high, with the highest entrapment percentage observed in formulae NE-A1 and NE-A2. This finding is consistent with previous reports (139,140).

Although there is a significant difference between NE-A1 and NE-A2 entrapment efficiency, however, the difference is small and when Putting all the investigated characteristics together, NE-A2 will defeat NE-A1 in most of them.

Figure (3.12) Entrapment efficiency percentage representing the eight formulae. The highest entrapment was represented by formulae NE-A1 and NE-A2. (i) EE% for formulae of different ratios of Smix (ii) EE% for formulae of different concentrations of oil (iii) EE% for formulae of different concentrations of Smix were separately shown.

Data are expressed as mean \pm SD, \$^* P \leq 0.05. (n=2)

3.5.9 Thermodynamic stability study

Different stress tests, including heating-cooling cycle, centrifugation and freeze-thaw cycle tests were performed on all the prepared formulae. The formula that passed these stress tests was subjected to further characterization tests. All of the prepared MXD-loaded NE formulae were successfully passed the thermodynamic stability test with no signs of phase separation, creaming, cracking, or drug precipitation, which may be found in macroemulsions (141). The results showed that all the preparations had good physical consistency, as shown in Table (3.6).

Table (3.6) Thermodynamic stability study for different MXD- loaded NEs formulae.

Formula code	Heating-cooling cycles	Centrifugation test	Freeze-thaw cycles
NE-A1	Pass	Pass	Pass
NE-A2			
NE-A3			
NE-A4			
NE-A5			
NE-A6			
NE-A7			
NE-A8			

3.6 Selection of optimized formulae

The selection of the optimized formula was made based on several criteria, which include the lowest droplet size, the acceptable polydispersity index (PDI), the highest zeta potential (ZP) and the high entrapment efficiency. The characterization results revealed that NE-A2 with Smix ratio (1:2), 5% oil concentration and 40% Smix concentration, is the selected formula. The NE-A2 formula has the lowest droplet size of 14.62 ± 1.36 nm, the lowest PDI of 0.22 ± 0.021 , the most acceptable zeta potential of -4.7 ± 0.6 mV and the high entrapment efficiency of $91.2 \pm 0.31\%$ compared with other formulae. The selected formula was subjected to further characterization studies as mentioned earlier in **section 2.3.6**.

3.6.1 Transmission electron microscopy (TEM)

TEM analysis has proven to be one of the most effective methods for determining morphology, structure, and particle size. The optimized MXD-loaded formula (NE-A2) was tested by using TEM to characterize the droplet size and morphology. The photomicrograph is represented in **Figure (3.13)**. TEM results of the selected formula show spherical droplets and well discrete with a homogeneous and uniform size that appeared to be less than 100 nm.

Moreover, this microscopic result supports our findings in the reported droplet size analysis, which was conducted using the dynamic light scattering technique (DLS). In addition, the result is in parallel with previous literature as reported by M. Kumar et al., who loaded the drug into NE and found that the droplet size of the optimized formula was in the range of 20-120 nm, which was confirmed by the TEM result and the droplet found was spherical and well discrete (142).

Figure (3.13) Photomicrographic representation of TEM of the selected MXD-loaded NE formula (NE-A2).

3.7 Preparation of MXD-loaded NEG formulae

The optimized MXD-loaded NE formula (NE-A2) was converted to NEG with the use of three different concentrations (0.1%, 0.2% and 0.3% (w/w)) of carbopol 934 as a gelling agent. The prepared NEG was subjected to further evaluation to determine the optimum polymer concentration for patient use.

3.8 Characterization of MXD-loaded NEG

3.8.1 Visual inspection

As demonstrated in **Table (3.7)** and **Figure (3.14)**, the three prepared NEG formulae exhibited a homogeneous yellow color and elegant appearance.

Table (3.7) Visual inspection of different MXD-loaded NEG formulae.

Visual inspection of prepared NEG formulae		
Formula code	Color	Homogeneity
NEG-A2x	Light yellow	Homogenous
NEG-A2y		
NEG-A2z		

Figure (3.14) Visual appearance of the different MXD-loaded NEG formulae. It shows yellowish and homogenous appearance NEG-A2x loaded with 0.1% (w/w) carbopol 934, NEG-A2y loaded with 0.2% (w/w) carbopol 934 and NEG-A2z loaded with 0.3% (w/w) carbopol 934. (red line determine the pourability of the prepared formulae).

3.8.2 Measurement of pH

The pH values of the developed MXD-loaded NEG formulae were illustrated in **Figure (3.15) (i)**. The pH levels were observed to be between 5.8 ± 0.05 and 6.2 ± 0.1 . This pH range is acceptable for topical formulations with no skin irritation. The results are compatible with previous literature by W. Soliman et al., who developed NEG formulation and demonstrated that its pH ranged from 5.5 to 6.4 (93).

It is worthy to mention that the observed reduction in pH is in parallel to the increase in the concentrations of carbopol 934. The significant difference observed

between the three formulae ($P \leq 0.05$) is attributed to the acidic nature of carbopol. This is logic as more carbopol means more acidic due to the carboxylic acid, which is contributed to the acidic nature of carbopol.

3.8.3 Measurement of spreadability

Spreadability is one of the most essential considerations for transdermal preparations. It depicts how the gel spreads easily when is applied to the skin. It has a direct impact on patient compliance. Spreadability has an inverse relationship with viscosity where it is reduced as the viscosity increases. The results are shown in **Figure (3.15) (ii)**.

The spreadability values for prepared NEG formulae were ranged from 18.4 ± 0.89 g.cm/s to 24.3 ± 0.67 g.cm/s and there were significant differences between the three formulae ($P \leq 0.05$). According to these results, the formula NEG-A2y showed optimum spreadability of 21.6 ± 0.70 g.cm/s and indicated that the NEG was easily spreadable with a minimal amount of shear. This finding complies with the result of work conducted by A. Dadwal et al. (102).

3.8.4 Measurement of viscosity

The topical application of NEG is preferred over the NE, as NEG is a viscous system with a viscosity more than NE and stays longer at the application site with possible delayed release. Carbopol 934 was incorporated into the developed formula to increase system viscosity and improve drug delivery (81). The results are displayed in **Figure (3.15) (iii)**. The results were shown that viscosity values were 93.3 ± 16.64 cp and 492.0 ± 87.81 cp for NEG-A2x and NEG-A2y respectively, and there is a significant difference between these two formulae ($P \leq 0.05$). It was noticed that the viscosity of NEG-A2z was not determined, because this formula is thick with a high viscosity.

The results are comparable with spreadability as both the viscosity and spreadability depend on the concentration of carbopol 934. Accordingly, the viscosity of the prepared NEG increased as the concentration of carbopol 934 increased. **Figure (3.14)** shows the different pourability of the prepared formulae, which could give an idea about the viscosity of each formula. It was observed that NEG-A2y has the optimum viscosity for NEG to be applied topically and this result was similar to a previously reported result by S. Bhattacharya et al. (143). The NEG-A2x was easily poured and had a relatively low viscosity. In accordance, it may have, a relatively short contact time.

Figure (3.15) Characterization of NEG in terms of pH (i), spreadability (ii), and viscosity (iii). Arrow bar in viscosity histogram represents viscosity higher than the machine capacity. The dotted line represents reference-based acceptable good quality. Data are expressed as mean \pm SD, *# $P \leq 0.05$. cp=centipoise.

3.8.5 In-vitro drug release

The drug should first be released from the vehicles before being partitioned into or absorbed by the skin during the biological permeation process. As a result, assessing in-vitro drug release is an important step in clearing the way for efficient penetration (144). The in-vitro drug release profile was conducted to evaluate the release of MXD from the optimized MXD-loaded NE formula (NE-A2) and all NEG formulae in comparison to the alcoholic standard solution and marketed solution in phosphate buffer solution pH 7.4.

The cumulative in-vitro drug release profile of MXD from six different formulae is represented in **Figure (3.16)**. The results demonstrated that both the optimized MXD-loaded NE formula (NE-A2) and the alcoholic standard solution showed around 99% cumulative drug release in 420 min. However, there is a reduction in the cumulative release profile of the marketed solution and the NEG formulae (NEG-A2x, NEG-A2y, and NEG-A2z).

The time required for each formula to achieve 50% and 80% cumulative release of MXD was measured and the interpolation analysis was made, and results were compared and were shown in **Figure (3.17)**. It was observed in **Figure (3.17) (i)** that the 50% cumulative drug release was achieved at different times and was ranked according to the following order, from fastest to slowest formulae: alcoholic standard solution = marketed solution > optimized MXD-loaded NE formula (NE-A2) > NEG formulae (NEG-A2x, NEG-A2y, and NEG-A2z). **Figure (3.17) (ii)** demonstrates that the 80% cumulative release was achieved at different times and was ranked in the following order: alcoholic standard solution > marketed solution > optimized MXD-loaded NE formula (NE-A2) > NEG formulae (NEG-A2x, NEG-A2y, and NEG-A2z).

The results are shown in **Figure (3.17)** indicate that the release from the optimized MXD-loaded NE formula (NE-A2) was significantly ($P \leq 0.05$) slower than that from the alcoholic standard solution under the same experimental conditions. This result is attributed to the presence of Smix, since a high Smix concentration might result in drug sequestration inside micelles or oil droplets, resulting in delayed drug release via dialysis bag. This finding was comply with the previous work reported by Ali and Hussein et al. (145). Another explanation by M. Maitra et al. concluded that poor drug partitioning between lipid and dissolving media may be the cause of somewhat delayed drug release in prepared NE formula. Furthermore, the lipophilic behavior of the drug is manifested by the release trend; as a result, the drug is likely to remain in the oil phase. Because of the hydrophobic nature of the outer hair cuticle, the in-vitro release profile favors trans-follicular delivery, which is expected to enhance drug penetration into the hair follicle. Furthermore, poor partitioning aids in drug retention in the hair follicle (146).

To make a comparison between different NEG formulae and alcoholic standard solution, the cumulative drug release of NEG-A2x, NEG-A2y and NEG-A2z were compared to the standard solution. It was illustrated in **Figure (3.17)** that the decrease in release rate in NEG formulae might be explained by the fact that when the viscosity of these formulations has increased, the drug-loaded oil droplets are covered by the polymeric surface. As a result, the drug should traverse a long and complicated pathway to reach the release medium, resulting in slowing drug diffusion through the dialysis membrane and lower release rates (81).

To study the effect of different carbopol concentrations on cumulative drug release, a comparison was made between (NEG-A2x, NEG-A2y, and NEG-A2z). The results shown in **Figures (3.16)** and **(3.17)**, indicated that there is no

significant difference ($p < 0.05$) between these three formulae and increasing the concentration of carbopol have induced a slight change but statistically non-significant effect on drug release. This may be attributed to using very low concentrations of carbopol 934 which may not have a perceptible effect on drug release. It is known that the release of drugs from the gel matrix is influenced by incorporating NE in a hydrogel system of different concentrations of gelling agent to produce NEG, according to D. Sandeep et al., the increase in the concentration of the gelling agent in the gel matrix decreases the rate of release and vice versa (147). The formula NEG-A2y achieved the highest drug release of $91.30 \pm 2.51\%$ at 420 min and was selected for further permeation study.

Figure (3.16) Cumulative release profile of different formulae. Six samples were tested (NEG-A2X, NEG-A2Y, NEG-A2Z, marketed solution, standard solution and NE-A2).

Data are expressed as mean \pm SD.

Figure (3.17) Interpolation of time against cumulative release at 50% (i) and 80% (ii). The tested samples (NEG-A2X, NEG-A2Y, NEG-A2Z, marketed solution, and NE-A2) were compared to the standard solution. Data are expressed as mean \pm SD. *# \$ $P \leq 0.05$ as compared to the standard solution.

3.8.5.1 Mathematical modelling of drug release

Different kinetic models (zero-order kinetics, first-order kinetics, Higuchi model, and Korsmeyer-Peppas's model) have been used to describe the kinetic release of MXD from optimized MXD-loaded NE formula (NE-A2), alcoholic standard solution, marketed solution, and NEG formulae (NEG-A2x, NEG-A2y, and NEG-A2z).

Release kinetic data of MXD from different formulae in phosphate buffer solution pH 7.4 is shown in **Table (3.8)**. The data analysis illustrates that marketed solution and NEG formulae have the highest regression coefficient (r^2), which fits with Higuchi's model. This suggests that diffusion is involved in the release mechanism of MXD from a drug delivery system (DDS). However, the optimized MXD-loaded NE formula (NE-A2) and alcoholic standard solution follow the

first-order kinetics in which the rate of drug release is directly proportional to the concentration of the drug (104).

Table (3.8) The correlation coefficient (r^2) of different kinetic models of different formulae. The comparison was made between optimized MXD-loaded NE formula (NE-A2), alcoholic standard solution, marketed solution and NEG formulae (NEG-A2x, NEG-A2y, and NEG-A2z) that were released in phosphate buffer solution pH 7.4.

Models	NEG-A2X	NEG-A2Y	NEG-A2Z	Standard Solution	Marketed solution	NE-A2
Zero-order	0.7830	0.7406	0.7427	0.3926	0.4509	0.7435
First-order	0.9328	0.9198	0.9201	0.8965	0.6056	0.9612
Higuchi	0.9444	0.9271	0.9214	0.6163	0.6808	0.9189
Korsmeyer	0.2490	0.2023	0.1976	0.0692	0.1020	0.2280

3.8.6 Ex-vivo permeation study

The optimized NEG formula (NEG-A2y) and marketed solution were subjected to an ex-vivo skin permeation study to validate and compare their penetration capabilities. NEG was reported to improve penetration rates in deep skin layers. Previous studies have shown that NEG can act as drug reservoirs, releasing drugs from the inner phase to the outer phase and, subsequently, into the skin. Various processes, such as the permeability improvement capability of different NEG components, might have resulted in improved transdermal drug delivery (43). Franz diffusion cells were used to investigate the ex-vivo permeation study (as mentioned in **section 2.3.8.6**). The amounts of MXD that permeated through the excised rat skin for the optimized MXD-loaded NEG formula (NEG-A2y) and the marketed solution in phosphate buffer solution pH

7.4 were evaluated, and the permeation profiles of both formulae were shown in **Figure (3.18)**. Based on the permeation study results, the cumulative amount of MXD that permeated through the skin over 24 hours from the NEG-A2y formula was $961.97 \pm 4.77 \mu\text{g}/\text{cm}^2$ and was significantly ($P \leq 0.05$) higher than that from the marketed solution $398.24 \pm 10.038 \mu\text{g}/\text{cm}^2$ so the NEG-A2y exhibited a better permeation profile than the marketed solution.

The values of the cumulative amount of drug permeated, flux rate, permeability coefficient (K_p), and enhancement ratio (E_r) were calculated and the results are shown in **Table (3.9)**. The results indicate that the steady-state transdermal flux (SSTF) for the NEG-A2y formula was equal to $38.005 \pm 0.02 \mu\text{g}/\text{cm}^2/\text{h}$ and was significantly higher ($P \leq 0.05$) than the marketed solution, which was equal to $16.54 \pm 0.45 \mu\text{g}/\text{cm}^2/\text{h}$. The permeability coefficient K_p was also significantly higher for NEG-A2y $3.80 \pm 0.0023 \times 10^{-3} \text{ cm}^2/\text{h}$ in comparison to the marketed solution $1.65 \pm 0.045 \times 10^{-3} \text{ cm}^2/\text{h}$. Therefore, the permeation enhancement ratio from the NEG-A2y formula to the marketed solution was 2.3 ± 0.06 folds.

Our findings are consistent with those of R. Kaur et al., who developed a transdermal NEG formulation of fluvastatin with nano-sized globules and concluded that the NEG formulation significantly improves permeation compared to the conventional solution formulation (134). A similar finding was also illustrated by M. Morsy et al. when they conducted an atorvastatin NEG permeation study. They concluded that the skin permeation potential of atorvastatin was significantly enhanced when formulated into NEG compared to the solution (148).

Many explanations were suggested to interpret the higher permeation of NEG than the conventional drug delivery systems. Because permeability is inversely

proportional to the size of the NE droplets, nano-sized droplets of optimized MXD-loaded NE formula (NE-A2) (as mentioned in section 3.5.5) equal to 14.62 ± 1.36 nm facilitated MXD penetration through various skin layers and improved permeation characteristics of the formula. Small nanodroplets settle down to close contact with the skin, giving a greater surface area for drug penetration and releasing high drug concentration on the affected region. As previously stated, the 50 nm size of NE droplets promote transdermal penetration (128). The incorporation of NE into carbopol 934 showed further improvement in ex-vivo permeation due to higher retention and contact time with skin. The presence of a non-ionic surfactant (i.e. Tween 80[®]) in the NE formula may greatly support and improve the permeation of MXD through the skin. Surfactant monomers have the ability to alter the integrity and function of a biological membrane, rendering drug entry easier (149).

The prepared NE formula was o/w type as was determined by measuring the conductivity test (see section 3.5.3), the external phase was water which may enhance the hydration of the SC and leads the corneum cells to expand, resulting in larger channels for drug passage and increased diffusivity of the lipophilic drugs (150). Another reason that may explain the high permeability may be due to the presence of clove oil, which contains eugenol, that has the ability to permeate the skin and to increase partitioning of MXD through the SC into the deeper skin layers (151). Moreover, the presence of co-solvent PG in the formulation may improve drug partitioning into skin layers through a variety of processes including lipid and protein extraction and SC swelling (152). In summary, the improved skin permeation could be due to the different components of NEG like clove oil, Tween 80[®] and propylene glycol that act synergistically and manifest penetration enhancement through the SC (38).

Figure (3.18) Permeation profiles of MXD through the excised rat skin. Both optimized NEG formula (NEG-A2y) and marketed solution were tested. Data are expressed as mean \pm SD. * $P \leq 0.05$ as compared to marketed solution.

Table (3.9): Permeation parameters for MXD from optimized MXD-loaded NEG formula (NEG-A2y) and marketed solution. Data are expressed as mean \pm SD. * $P \leq 0.05$ as compared to marketed solution.

Permeation parameters	Formula code	
	NEG-A2y	Marketed solution
Cumulative amount (Q, $\mu\text{g}/\text{cm}^2$)	961.97 \pm 4.77*	398.24 \pm 10.038
Flux rate (Jss, $\mu\text{g}/\text{cm}^2/\text{h}$)	38.005 \pm 0.02*	16.54 \pm 0.45
Permeability coefficient Kp (cm^2/h) * 10^{-3}	3.80 \pm 0.0023*	1.65 \pm 0.045
Enhancement ratio (Er)	2.3 \pm 0.06	
* $P < 0.05$		

3.8.7 Pharmacodynamics study

3.8.7.1 The muscle relaxant effects of MXD on bladder segments pre-contracted with pilocarpine

The vasodilator effect of MXD was tested on smooth muscle segments isolated from sheep bladder tissue, the relaxant effect of optimized MXD-loaded NE formula (NE-A2) compared to marketed solutions were shown in **Figures (3.19) and (3.20)**. Results showed that the average relaxation percentage for NE-A2 was equal to $76.73 \pm 7.49\%$ while that for the marketed solution was $14.59 \pm 1.23\%$. Thus, the developed NE-A2 formula possessed a better pharmacological effect when compared to the marketed solution with a statistically highly significant difference ($P \leq 0.001$).

Results also revealed that acute application of MXD induced concentration-dependent relaxation in sheep bladder segments pre-contracted submaximally with pilocarpine. The mechanism involved K^+ channel opening. However, MXD could also block Ca^{2+} influx (153).

Hair growth depends primarily on MXD concentration. In general, topical MXD is regarded as a safe drug; nevertheless, some individuals suffered from adverse effects such as irritating dermatitis, itching, and scaling following treatment. Research by J. McCoy et al found that increasing the topical MXD concentration, in patients expected to be non-responders, by up to 15% enhanced clinical response compared to those associated with 5% (154). In the current work, MXD NEG was formulated with the same concentration of solutions commercially available as an attempt to improve pharmacodynamics effects with reduction of the possible adverse effects that might be induced with MXD higher concentrations. Results are shown in **Figure (3.20)** indicated that the

pharmacological efficacy was improved by 5 folds when MXD was formulated as a NE in comparison with the solution.

From a pharmaceutical point of view, the NE drug delivery system was documented to have a longer residence time and may penetrate larger surface areas, resulting in improved drug uptake in comparison with MXD solution (155). Our findings might be attributed to the nano-size of the optimized MXD-loaded NE formula (NE-A2) and the high penetration of the prepared NE. The NE excipients particularly Tween 80[®] and clove oil as surfactant and oil phase, respectively, could act synergistically and interpret our finding which was discussed earlier in the previous section.

Figure (3.19) Original organ bath trace for MXD induced bladder tissue relaxation: KCl (60 mM) bath concentrations were obtained for standardization, after about 15 min the tissue was washed out with Krebs-Henseleit, then pilocarpine was added to stimulate tissue contraction before the addition of a single concentration of MXD NE. Control tissues treated with MXD marketed solution.

Figure (3.20) Muscle relaxation effect of MXD from marketed solution and optimized MXD-loaded NE formula NE-A2. The sheep bladder segments were pre-contracted with pilocarpine. Data are expressed as a percentage relaxation of the pilocarpine-induced contraction and mean \pm SD from 4-different animals.

3.8.8 Fourier Transform Infrared Spectroscopy (FTIR) of MXD-loaded NEG

FTIR technique was used to investigate any type of interference between the components of the optimal MXD-loaded NEG formula sample (NEG-A2y). FTIR analysis of the MXD-loaded NEG (NEG-A2y) was shown in **Figure (3.21)** and **Table (3.10)**. The FTIR chart analysis revealed that most of the distinct peaks of MXD were in their correct positions. The N-H stretching band appeared on the broadband with a shift towards a lower wavenumber. This indicated the formation of inter-and intramolecular hydrogen bonds that caused the appearance of broadband in the N-H stretch band and without a chemical reaction between MXD and other excipients, which means maintaining chemical stability in the formula (93).

Table (3.10) FTIR Spectrum band assignments of optimized MXD-loaded NEG formula (NEG-A2y).

No	IR bands γ cm ⁻¹	Assignment groups (Stretching bands)
1	3344.73	N-H broadband with hydrogen bond
2	2975.67, 2925.54	C-H cyclic aliphatic (CH ₂)
3	1642.25	C=N
5	1248.58	N-O

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Figure (3.21) FTIR spectra for a sample of optimized MXD-loaded NEG formula (red box indicates the spectral band assignment of MXD powder).

3.8.9 Stability study at different storage conditions

The optimized MXD-loaded NEG formula (NEG-A2y) was subjected to stability study at different storage conditions and the physical characteristics were assessed in compliance with ICH guidelines. The data from the stability testing was shown in **Table (3.11)**. The formula NEG-A2y was checked visually and the result showed no significant change in color, homogeneity and pH at different temperatures (i.e. 6°C, 25°C, and 45°C) in comparison to the freshly prepared formula. However, a significant change in electrical conductivity measurements ($p \leq 0.05$) were observed in different storage conditions, but this difference is worthless because the electrical conductivity remained above 10 $\mu\text{S}/\text{cm}$, indicating that the type of emulsion was maintained as o/w.

Retaining stability means that the formula NEG-A2y did not degrade over the test period. The presence of a gelling agent in the NEG-A2y might result in such stability. Our findings are consistent with those of M. Mohamed et al., who discovered the critical role of gelling agents in preparation stability (156).

Table (3.11) Physical characterization of optimized MXD-loaded NEG formula (NEG-A2y) following 3months of storage at 6°C, 25 °C and 45 °C.

parameter		6±2 °C	25±2 °C	45±2 °C
	Day 0	Day 30	Day 60	Day 90
Color	Light yellow	Light yellow	Light yellow	Light yellow
Homogeneity	Homogenous	Homogenous	Homogenous	Homogenous
pH	6 ±0.08 ^{ns}	6 ±0.23 ^{ns}	5.9 ±0.8 ^{ns}	5.9 ±0.52 ^{ns}
Electrical conductivity $\mu\text{S}/\text{cm}$	52 ±0.72*	54 ±0.39	56 ±0.34	53 ±0.53 [#]
	* $p \leq 0.05$ as compared to Day 60, [#] $p \leq 0.05$ as compared to Day 30 and 60 ns=non-significant. Data are expressed as mean ±SD			

(Chapter Four)

Conclusions

And

Recommendations

4 Conclusion and recommendations

4.1 Conclusion

Based on the results obtained from the current study, the following points could be concluded:

- 1.** NE is considered as an advanced drug delivery system for the incorporation of poorly water-soluble drugs (lipophilic drug molecules) into aqueous-based formulations.
- 2.** The selected mixture of clove oil (as oil phase), Tween 80[®] (as surfactant), ethanol (as co-surfactant) and PG (as co-solvent) has good compatibility and self-emulsification ability.
- 3.** MXD was easily incorporated into such a dispersed nanocarrier system and the produced NEs were successfully developed using the low-energy method concurrently with the high-speed homogenizer.
- 4.** All the prepared MXD-loaded NE formulae passed the thermodynamic stability tests and have droplet sizes in the nanometric scale and uniform droplet size distribution.
- 5.** The selected MXD-loaded NE formula (NE-A2) exhibited particles in the nanometer range (14.62 ± 1.36 nm) with homogeneous distribution (PDI is 0.22 ± 0.021) and acceptable stability.
- 6.** Carbopol 934 was an excellent choice for the preparation of the MXD NEG system when used at a concentration of 0.2%, which resulted in optimum viscosity and acceptable spreadability.
- 7.** The MXD release profile from NE and NEG formulae after seven hours revealed a satisfactory and adequate release.

8. The ex-vivo permeation study of the selected formula of NEG showed an adequate penetration of MXD across skin layers over 24 hours of the experiment.
9. Using the organ bath system as a model (with sheep bladder tissue) seems to be an effective method to evaluate the pharmaco-dynamic efficacy of the prepared MXD NE.
10. The pharmaco-dynamic study showed that the optimized MXD-loaded NE formula (NE-A2) is 5 folds more efficacious than the marketed solution.
11. A stability study confirmed that the optimized MXD-loaded NEG formula (NEG-A2y) has acceptable stability in the condition of storage for three months.

4.2 Recommendations and future work

- 1.** Further study on preparation of nanoemulsion through using different types of oils such as oleic acid.
- 2.** Further study on preparation of nanoemulsion through using different high-energy methods such as ultrasonication and high-pressure homogenizer.
- 3.** Conducting the in-vitro release study and permeation study using different conditions like different pH, different times and using human skin (cadaver) if possible.
- 4.** Conducting a rheology study to determine the type of flow whether dilatant or pseudoplastic flow.
- 5.** Conducting a clinical study on animals or human volunteers using the selected formula of nanoemulgel in comparison to the pharmaceutical preparations available in the market.

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Appendix

Appendix-1 Particle size analysis report of optimized MXD-loaded NE formula (NE-A2)

Standard report

Created by: GLOBAL-PC
Created at: 3/17/2021 1:16:32 PM

General

Name	Untitled 1	User	GLOBAL-PC
Method		Time	3/14/2021 11:30:36 AM
Status	Succeeded	Instrument type	Litesizer 500
Measurement type	ISO Particle size analysis		

Settings

Measurement cell	Omega Cuvette	Equilibration time	0h 01m 00s
Angle	Automatic	Analysis model	General
Target temperature	25.0 °C	Cumulant model	Advanced

Quality

Quality mode	Automatic	Measurement time	0h 00m 10s
Number of runs	60		

Filter

Attenuation mode	Automatic	Attenuation	0
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Focus

Focus mode	Automatic	Focus position	0.0 mm
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Material

Name	Polystyrene Latex	Refractive index Laser 1	1.5850
Absorption Laser 1	0.0010		

Solvent

Name	Water	Refractive index	1.3303
Viscosity	0.8903 mPa.s		

Statistics table

Name	Hydrodynamic diameter	Peak 1 (intensity)	Peak 2 (intensity)	Peak 3 (intensity)
Mean value	14.62 nm	18.14 nm	- nm	- nm
Standard deviation	1.36 nm	3.79 nm	- nm	- nm
Rel. standard deviation	9.33 %	20.90 %	- %	- %

Kalliope version: 2.8.3
Serial number: 82807900

Measurement completed successfully
Page 1 of 2

Measurements (intensity)

Name	Temperature [°C]	Processed runs	Measurement position [mm]	Polydispersity index [%]	Hydrodynamic diameter [nm]	Peak 1 (intensity) [nm]	Peak 2 (intensity) [nm]	Peak 3 (intensity) [nm]	Diffusion Coefficient [μm²/s]	Color
A2-PS 1	25.0	6	0.0	24.5	16.15	22.50	-	-	30.4	—
A2-PS 2	25.0	6	0.0	22.4	14.14	16.36	-	-	34.7	—
A2-PS 3	25.0	6	0.0	20.3	13.55	15.57	-	-	36.2	—

Particle size distribution by intensity

Comment

Appendix-2 Zeta potential report of optimized MXD-loaded NE formula (NE-A2)

Standard report

Created by: GLOBAL-PC
Created at: 3/17/2021 1:17:23 PM

Statistics

Name	Mean zeta potential	Distribution peak	Conductivity	Electrophoretic Mobility
Mean value	-4.7 mV	-4.6 mV	0.063 mS/cm	-0.3663 $\mu\text{m}^2\text{cm/Vs}$
Standard deviation	0.6 mV	1.6 mV	0.000 mS/cm	0.0473 $\mu\text{m}^2\text{cm/Vs}$
Rel. standard deviation	12.91 %	33.63 %	0.13 %	12.91 %

Measurements

Name	Temperature [°C]	Processed runs	Mean zeta potential [mV]	Distribution peak [mV]	Conductivity [mS/cm]	Electrophoretic Mobility [$\mu\text{m}^2\text{cm/Vs}$]	Color
A2-ZETA 1	25.0	1000	-4.1	-6.4	0.063	-0.3196	—
A2-ZETA 2	25.0	660	-5.3	-4.0	0.063	-0.4142	—
A2-ZETA 3	25.0	1000	-4.7	-3.5	0.063	-0.3651	—

Zeta potential distribution

Appendix-3 Ethical committee approval

University of Mosul
College of Veterinary Medicine
Institutional Animal Care and Use Committee

Date: 24/6/2021
Ref: UM.VET.2021.004

Project title: Preparation, in-vitro evaluation and pharmacodynamic study of minoxidil topical nanoemulgel

Researchers: Alaa Rakan Azeez
Myasar Alkotaji

Number of approved animals: 12

Research area: College of pharmacy/ industrial pharmacy lab.

Duration: 1/4/2021 — 1/10/2021

A handwritten signature in blue ink, appearing to be 'A' followed by a long horizontal stroke.

Assistant. Prof. Dr. Ahmed Khalaf Al-Jobory
Chairman,
Institutional Animal Care and Use Committee
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الخلاصة

الصلع الوراثي هو نوع شائع من تساقط الشعر واضطراب جلدي واسع الانتشار. يعتبر دواء المينوكسيديل موسع وعائي قوي معتمد من قبل إدارة الغذاء والدواء الأمريكية كمحلول موضعي أو رغوة لعلاج الصلع الوراثي. على الرغم من ذلك، فإن توصيل المينوكسيديل من المحاليل الموضعية التقليدية يعاني من قصر وقت التلامس مع فروة الرأس، وضعف اختراق الأنسجة، ومتطلبات الجرعات العالية. يهدف هذا العمل إلى تحضير هلام للمستحلب النانوي للمينوكسيديل (نانوايمولجيل) بهدف إطالة وقت التلامس مع فروة الرأس وتحسين التأثيرات الديناميكية الدوائية.

تم اجراء دراسات أولية لأيجاد الاختيار المناسب للطور الزيتي وخافض التوتر السطحي ونسب خافض التوتر السطحي الى خافض التوتر السطحي المشترك. تم تحضير ثمانية صيغ من مستحلب النانو المحمل بالمينوكسيديل وإخضاعها لدراسات استقصائية مختلفة مثل قياس الأس الهيدروجيني، التوصيل الكهربائي، نسبة نفاذية الضوء، محتوى الدواء وكفاءة التحميل، وحجم القطرة، مؤشر التشنج المتعدد، فرق الجهد السطحي، ودراسات الاستقرار الديناميكي الحراري لتحديد الصيغة المثلى. بعد ذلك، خضعت الصيغة المحسنة لمزيد من الدراسات مثل إطلاق الدواء في المختبر، والفحص المجهر الإلكتروني ودراسات ديناميكيات الدواء.

في الجزء الثاني من الدراسة، تم تحضير ثلاث صيغ نانوايمولجيل مختلفة محملة بالمينوكسيديل باستخدام الصيغة المختارة من مستحلب النانو مع ثلاثة تركيزات مختلفة من كاربوبول 934. خضعت صيغ النانو ايمولجل المحضرة لمزيد من دراسات التوصيف مثل توافق السواغات الدوائية بواسطة FTIR، قياس الأس الهيدروجيني، القابلية للانتشار، اللزوجة، إطلاق الدواء في المختبر، دراسات اختراق الغشاء الحيوي ودراسة الثبات في ظل ظروف تخزين مختلفة لتحديد أفضل تركيبة نانوايمولجل للمينوكسيديل.

أظهرت النتائج أن تركيبة مستحلب النانو NE-A2 المحملة بالمينوكسيديل مع نسبة (2: 1) Smix وتركيز الزيت بنسبة 5% وتركيز Smix بنسبة 40% كانت الصيغة المختارة. أظهرت نتائج المجهر الإلكتروني للصيغة المختارة قطرات كروية بقطر أقل من 100 نانومتر. فيما أظهرت الدراسة الديناميكية الدوائية أن متوسط نسبة الانبساط العضلي لصيغة مستحلب النانو المحسن NE-A2 كان يساوي 76,73% ± 7,490، بينما كانت النسبة للمحلول الموجود في السوق 14,09% ± 1,233.

أظهرت نتائج التوصيف الخاصة بالصيغة المختارة للمينوكسيديل NEG-A2y أن الصيغة تحتوي على قيمة اس هيدروجيني مقبولة مع قابلية انتشار مثالية (٢١,٦ ± ٠,٧٠) g.cm / s، ولزوجة مثلى (٤٩٢ ± ٨١,٨١ cp). أظهر سلوك التحرر في المختبر الخاص بتركيبية مستحلب النانو المحمل بالمينوكسيديل المُحسَّنة NE-A2 تحرراً أعلى من تلك الخاصة بالمحلول القياسي والمستحضر الموجود في الأسواق. وقد لوحظ أن الإطلاق التراكمي لصيغة النانوإيمولجيل nanoemulgel المُحسَّنة التي تحتوي على المينوكسيديل NEG -A2y أبداً من المحلول الكحولي القياسي والمحلول الموجود في الأسواق.

استناداً إلى نتائج دراسة النفاذية عبر الغشاء الحي، أظهرت صيغة NEG-A2y المحسَّنة للنانوإيمولجيل اختراق أفضل من المحلول الموجود في السوق والكمية التراكمية للمينوكسيديل التي تغلغت عبر الجلد على مدار ٢٤ ساعة من صيغة NEG-A2y كانت ٩٦١,٩٧ ± ٤,٧٧ µg/cm²، وهو أعلى بكثير من المحلول المتوفر في السوق، ٣٩٨,٢٤ ± ١٠,٠٣ µg/cm².

تم فحص صيغة النانوإيمولجيل المختارة (NEG-A2y) للتأكد من ثباتها، وتبين أن الصيغة مستقرة عند درجات حرارة مختلفة.

خلصت الدراسة الحالية إلى أن النانوإيمولجيل يعتبر تقنية متقدمة لتعزيز إيصال الدواء مع وقت ملامس طويل واختراق للأغشية محسن، وما يترتب على ذلك من تحسين التأثير الديناميكي لدواء المينوكسيديل.

جمهورية العراق
وزارة التعليم العالي والبحث العلمي
جامعة الموصل
كلية الصيدلة

التحضير والتقييم والدراسة الديناميكية الدوائية لهلام المستحلب النانوي الموضوعي لعقار المينوكسديل

رسالة

مقدمة للجنة الدراسات العليا

كلية الصيدلة / جامعة الموصل

كجزء من متطلبات الحصول على شهادة الماجستير في الصيدلة

من قبل

علاء رakan عزيز

(بكالوريوس صيدلة ٢٠١٢)

المشرفون

المدرس

د هاني مهدي المختار

دكتوراه ادوية

الأستاذ المساعد

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دكتوراه صيدلانيات

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